

**Strategic Analysis of a Low-Carbon and Cost-Effective Power
System in Saudi Arabia by 2030**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are the original and have not been submitted in whole or in any part for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements. This short-format dissertation contains fewer than 13700 words excluding appendices, bibliography, footnotes, tables and equations and has fewer than 36 figures.

Faisal Albanmi

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Abstract

Saudi Arabia is undergoing transformative changes in its power sector as part of its broader Vision 2030 agenda, presenting a unique opportunity to reshape its energy landscape. With a national target of achieving 50% electricity generation from renewable sources by 2030, the Kingdom is not only rethinking its energy mix but also actively investing in innovations that support decarbonization and long-term cost-effectiveness. These shifts open up strategic opportunities to design a modern power system that aligns with both national ambitions and global climate responsibilities. This dissertation presents a comprehensive strategic analysis of Saudi Arabia's pathway to a low-carbon and economically viable power grid by 2030. It begins with an in-depth review of the Kingdom's power sector development, historical emissions, and policy targets under Vision 2030. The study then explores the country's renewable energy potential, focusing on solar and wind resources, while also assessing the role of emerging low-carbon technologies, such as hydrogen, carbon capture, utilization and storage (CCUS), and large-scale energy storage systems. To evaluate system performance and identify the most viable future grid configurations, the project employs PyPSA (Python for Power System Analysis), an open-source modelling framework, to simulate generation scenarios, optimize the energy mix, and analyse trade-offs between cost and emissions. Through this modelling effort, the study estimates the Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE) across technologies and assesses the overall system's carbon impact, offering insights into the most strategic and practical pathways forward. Ultimately, this work aims to provide actionable guidance for policymakers and stakeholders on how to structure Saudi Arabia's future power system in a way that balances energy security, affordability, and sustainability.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

Rapid decarbonisation of the global energy system has become imperative to limit warming to well below 2 °C in line with the Paris Agreement. Electricity generation accounts for roughly 40% of worldwide carbon dioxide emissions [1], making the power sector a critical focus for climate mitigation and decarbonisation which involves replacing carbon-intensive fuels with renewable sources, improving energy efficiency while maintaining reliability and affordability, and deploying carbon capture technologies. Countries with hydrocarbon-rich economies face additional challenges because a large share of power generation is tied to fossil fuel. Saudi Arabia, where fossil fuels still account for the vast majority of electricity generation, undergoes the transformation of its power sector toward low-carbon technologies aligned with national and global climate goals. Saudi Arabia’s overall emissions represent almost 1.94 % of worlds CO₂ emissions accounting for 736.2 Mt of CO₂ according to Our World In Data [2].

FIGURE 1 ANNUAL CO₂ EMISSIONS, 2023 [2]

Saudi Arabia’s power sector has been relying on crude oil and natural gas for decades, and with population growth and industrial development, domestic oil consumption has reached 7.58 EJ [3]. Although this heavy reliance on oil and gas has ensured reliable electricity supply, fuelled economic growth, and ensured a 100% electricity access to all the population [4], but it has also contributed to rising CO₂ emissions of more than 200% since 2000 [2].

Recent statistics on installed generation units’ capacity show that Saudi Arabia’s power system remains overwhelmingly geared toward fossil fuels [5]. Gas-fired power plants constitute a

large block of capacity, while various liquid fuels, ranging from heavy and crude oil to diesel, collectively make up a slightly larger portion [5]. Together, these conventional sources contribute well over 98% of available generating capacity [5].

In contrast, Saudi Arabia has shown early signs of diversifications. Utility-scale solar and wind installations now appear in the capacity statistics, although at a very small scale, amounting to a tiny fraction of the overall fleet [5]. The presence of these renewable units indicates that Saudi Arabia is beginning to take advantage of its abundant solar irradiance and favourable wind corridors. Although renewables still represent only a token share of total capacity, their inclusion underscores the first steps toward a more balanced mix. The overall picture, therefore, is one of a system still firmly anchored to conventional energy sources but tentatively expanding into cleaner technologies as the country seeks to align its electricity sector with broader economic and environmental objectives.

Over recent years the carbon intensity of Saudi Arabia's power sector has improved but remains high. The CO₂ emission factor for electricity and heat generation stood at about 651 t CO₂ per GWh in 2017, and by 2022 it had fallen only to around 605 t CO₂ per GWh [6]. In 2022, as shown in Figure 2, the sector still released roughly 247 million tonnes of CO₂, with gas-fuelled plants producing about 43% of those emissions and oil-fuelled plants 57% [6]. These numbers show a slight enhancement but underline how far carbon intensity must fall to approach regional and global averages, for which scaling up renewable and low-carbon generation is therefore essential if emissions per kilowatt-hour are to drop significantly further.

FIGURE 2 ELECTRICITY GENERATION CO₂ EMISSIONS IN SAUDI ARABIA [6]

1.2 Motivation – Vision 2030

In April 2016 Saudi Arabia unveiled Vision 2030, an ambitious strategy to diversify the economy, reduce dependence on oil revenues and improve the quality of life for citizens. The National Renewable Energy Programme (NREP), announced within Vision 2030, sets a target of 50% renewable electricity by 2030, implying that half of domestic power should come from sources such as solar and wind [7]. The Saudi Green Initiative (SGI), launched in 2021, reinforces this commitment by aiming to reduce carbon emissions by more than 278 Mt per year by 2030 and plant 10 billion trees [8]. SGI contains over 85 programmes covering renewable energy deployment, carbon capture and nature conservation, with investment exceeding SAR 705 billion [8]. These initiatives demonstrate the Kingdom's determination to turn its natural and financial advantages into sustainable growth.

Vision 2030's renewable targets have evolved over time and have become progressively more ambitious. Early versions set a goal of installing 9.5 GW of renewable capacity by 2023; subsequent updates envisage expanding capacity to 130 GW by 2030 [9] [7]. Saudi Arabia wants to produce 58.7 GW of renewables comprising of 40 GW of solar, 16 GW of wind, and 2.7 GW of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) [10]. These numbers reflect the scale of opportunity. Building on successful projects such as Sudair solar (1.5 GW) and Dumat Al Jandal wind farm (0.4 GW), the Kingdom can leverage economies of scale, declining technology costs and international partnerships to accelerate deployment [11].

Beyond renewable generation, Vision 2030 embraces the Circular Carbon Economy (CCE), a framework that emphasises reducing, reusing, recycling and removing carbon [7]. Technologies such as carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS), green hydrogen production and large-scale energy storage are highlighted [7]. The NREP also contemplates integration of energy storage systems and grid interconnections with neighbouring countries to enhance flexibility and reliability. These initiatives suggest a holistic transformation, one that builds on the Kingdom's strengths.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

The central aims of this dissertation are outlined in three aspects. First, it seeks to examine the historical evolution of Saudi Arabia's power sector alongside the policy frameworks and renewable energy potential that underpin the country's vision 2030 ambitions. Second, the

research aims to evaluate the contribution of emerging and low-carbon technological solutions, including solar and wind technologies, carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) and hydrogen. Third, the project will explore optimal combinations of renewable and conventional generation technologies capable of delivering a low-carbon and cost-effective power system by 2030. While considering its reliability against intermittent renewable generation. By examining the existing landscape, the study will assess the pathways to facilitating a transition towards a low-carbon electricity system.

To achieve these aims, the dissertation pursues a set of specific objectives. These include:

- 1 Examining Saudi Arabia's power-sector goals and emission-mitigation commitments under Vision 2030;
- 2 Conducting a literature review of the current power system, with particular attention to historical greenhouse-gas and CO₂ emissions;
- 3 Reviewing the country's renewable-energy resource base, including solar irradiation and wind speeds;
- 4 Analysing the prospects for emerging low-carbon technologies such as CCUS, hydrogen and advanced storage;
- 5 Performing a high-level economic comparison of different generation technologies to assess cost-effectiveness;
- 6 Modelling a low-carbon and cost-effective power system for 2030 using available data or reasonable assumptions where data are unavailable; and
- 7 Calculating levelised costs of electricity for the alternative generation mixes under consideration.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Energy Systems Overview in Saudi Arabia

2.1.1 Energy Mix

Saudi Arabia's energy system is currently based on hydrocarbons. Figure 3 shows the increasing energy supply in the last three decades and shows that in 2022 the country's total energy supply (TES) amounted to roughly just over 10 exajoules [12]. Oil remained the dominant source, accounting for 64.2 % of TES (about 6.5 EJ), while natural gas provided 35.7 % (around 3.6 EJ) [12]. The contribution from wind, solar and other renewables was negligible, about 0.1 % of supply, equivalent to 9 100 terajoules with biofuels and waste adding only 333 TJ [12]. In other words, more than 99 % of Saudi Arabia's energy supply still comes from fossil fuels. This composition reflects the country's status as one of the world's largest oil and gas producers and its long-standing reliance on these resources to fuel domestic power generation, desalination plants, transport and industry.

FIGURE 3 TOTAL ENERGY SUPPLY (TES) BY SOURCE, SAUDI ARABIA, 1990-2022 [12]

As shown in figure 3, The evolution of supply over the last 20 years illustrates both growth and gradual diversification, as between 2000 and 2015 the quantity of energy supplied from oil rose steadily from 3 EJ to a peak of nearly 6.7 EJ, reflecting rapid expansion in electricity demand and oil-processing activities. After 2015 oil supply was steady and even dropped slightly during 2015–2022. In contrast, natural gas supply has more than doubled since 2000, rising from about 0.8 EJ to 3.6 EJ in 2022 as new gas processing facilities came online and policies encouraged switching from oil-fired to gas-fired power plants [12].

In 2022 Saudi Arabia’s total final energy consumption (TFC) approached 6.8 EJ [12]. As shown in figure 4, oil products, such as gasoline, diesel and fuel oil, constituted 65% of this total, underscoring the dominance of hydrocarbons in transport and industrial processes. Natural gas made up 17.2% of TFC, reflecting its growing role in power and industry [12]. Electricity accounted for 17.1%, about 1.155×10^{18} joules (or 1.155 EJ), highlighting the rapid expansion of electrical demand for cooling, lighting and industrial applications [12]. Direct use of crude oil in final consumption was small (about 0.6 %) but nonetheless indicative of continued reliance on oil-fired boilers and dual-fuel generators [12]. Historical data show that TFC has more than tripled since 1990, rising from roughly 2 EJ to today’s 6.8 EJ [12]. Oil products have dominated throughout, yet the shares of natural gas and electricity have risen. Per-capita electricity use reached 10,460 kWh in 2022, one of the highest levels in the Middle East, illustrating both improved access and high consumption in an affluent, energy-intensive society [12].

FIGURE 4 TOTAL FINAL CONSUMPTION TFC IN SAUDI ARABIA 2022 [12]

These data show a picture of an energy economy still deeply embedded in hydrocarbons yet diversifying. The dominance of oil in TES has improved with the expansion of natural gas infrastructure. Renewables remain growing, noting that those data are in 2022 and later in this chapter, the growth in renewables from 2022 till 2025 will be discussed, emphasising the scale of the challenge Saudi Arabia faces in moving toward its Vision 2030 objective of sourcing half of its electricity from renewables. To shift the balance, the country will need to accelerate investments in solar and wind as well as the liquid fuel displacement.

2.1.2 CO₂ Emissions

In Chapter 1 this thesis touched on the emissions implications of Saudi Arabia's electricity sector, a fuller picture emerges when looking at national CO₂ inventories. The IEA's fuel-combustion data show that total CO₂ emissions rose from roughly 150 Mt in 1990 to about 533 Mt in 2022 [12]. Oil remains the dominant source, releasing around 344 Mt CO₂ (64%) in 2022, while natural gas contributed about 189 Mt CO₂ (35%) [12]. Sectoral breakdowns illustrate the central role of electricity, according to the IEA, these activities account for roughly 49 % (260 Mt CO₂) of Saudi Arabia's energy-related CO₂ emissions, with the remainder coming mainly from transport and industry [12]. The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) arrives at a slightly lower estimate, as shown in figure 2, suggesting that electricity generation represents about 40 % of national emissions and noting that the power sector emitted 247 Mt CO₂ in 2022, with 57 % of those emissions from oil-fired units and 43 % from gas-fired plants [6]. Both sets of data indicate that coal play no role in Saudi Arabia's emissions profile.

FIGURE 5 CO₂ EMISSIONS BY SECTOR IN SAUDI ARABIA 1990-2022 [12]

Despite the continued dominance of fossil fuels, some indicators show gradual decarbonisation. The IEA's power-sector carbon-intensity index, which is normalised to 100 in 1992, had fallen to 76.46 by 2022, reflecting efficiency improvements and the substitution of oil with natural gas [12]. Similarly, the CO₂-to-energy-supply ratio declined from about 62 t CO₂/TJ in 1990 to 52.5 t CO₂/TJ in 2022, since the TES was about 10x10⁶ EJ and CO₂ emissions for the same year was 533 Mt [12]. Even so, absolute emissions from electricity have increased steadily, and avoided emissions from renewable energy remain marginal. Achieving

significant reductions will require not only continued fuel switching from oil to gas but also large-scale deployment of low-carbon generation technologies.

2.2 Power Systems in Saudi Arabia

This section represents the literature backbone of this thesis, as it sheds the light on the current status of Saudi Arabia's in its national power sector. This section will give insight on the conventional power taking a huge share of today's electricity mix in Saudi Arabia, its renewable progress, and the national future trajectory towards increasing its renewable contribution to 50% by 2030 [7].

Electricity Consumption represent almost 17% of the total final energy consumption in the country and account for almost 49% of the total emissions [12]. Based on the 2023 statistical booklet from the Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority, the capacity of generation units by primary fuel was still heavily weighted toward conventional sources: natural-gas-fired units accounted for around 42 GW of capacity, heavy fuel oil 22.6 GW, crude oil 19 GW, and diesel 6.2 GW, hence, the installed generation units' capacity for gas represent 46%, liquid fuel 52.4% [5]. The booklet also shows a small but growing contribution from renewable units, about 1.4 GW (1.5%) of capacity, reflecting the early stages of Saudi Arabia's move into solar and wind [5].

Whereas, for the same year 2023, statistical data, from Ember, shows the dispatched energy mix for the country's power grid all over the year, with gas taking partaking with a share of 62.7%, 46% oil and 1.3% renewables [13]. When set against the country's total installed capacity, this underscores how much headroom there is for renewable growth, and shows the country's commitment to reduce the liquid-fuel-fired generation. Figure 6, shows the reduction of burning liquid fuel in electricity generation from 2015 by almost 35 TWh [13].

FIGURE 6 LIQUID FOSSIL FUEL ELECTRICITY GENERATION FROM 2000 TO 2023 [13]

As part of the country's Vision 2030 energy strategy, the Kingdom has set an ambitious target of installing 130 GW of renewable energy capacity by the year 2030, with a dispatchable capacity of 58.7 GW, comprising of 40 GW of solar and most of the remainder is from wind [10]. This commitment reflects a strategic pivot, instead of consuming domestic oil for electricity, Saudi Arabia aims to free up resources for export, improve emissions profiles, and stimulate local manufacturing. As of 2025, the cumulative installed, under-development, and tendered renewable capacity exceeds 50 GW, spread across locations from Al Jawf in the north to Jazan in the southwest [11]. The map in figure 7 visually illustrates the geographic distribution of renewable projects across the Kingdom, categorized by development status and size.

FIGURE 7 GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF SAUDI ARABIA’S SOLAR AND WIND RENEWABLE ENERGY PROJECTS BY CAPACITY, TYPE, AND DEVELOPMENT STATUS [11]

To give a zoom in of the current ongoing renewable projects, figure 8 shows a detailed breakdown of the solar and wind projects annual added capacity by status with its expected commissioning year. For this year, 2025, only 1 project is remaining underdevelopment, and all the previous years expected commissioning were met, which shows the national dedication to meeting the goals on time.

FIGURE 8 ANNUAL ADDED RENEWABLE CAPACITY BY STATUS [11]

2.2.1 Conventional Power

Our World In Data’s published data shows that the electricity generation in Saudi Arabia in 2024 is almost 454 TWh [14]. Figure 9 shows Saudi Arabia’s electricity mix reveal a clear transition from oil-fired generation toward gas and a small but growing contribution from

renewables. In the mid-1980s the country generated roughly half of its electricity from oil, with the remainder coming mostly from associated gas [14]. Through the 1990s and early 2000s oil retained a slight majority, but the balance began to shift decisively after 2010 as new gas-fired capacity came online. By 2024 gas supplied about 63 % of electricity, while oil’s share had fallen to roughly 35 %. Renewables, though still tiny in absolute terms, have finally appeared in the mix: solar photovoltaics contributed around 1.8 % of generation in 2024, and wind supplied just 0.35 %. Coal, hydro, nuclear and bioenergy remained absent [14]. The overall trend points toward a gradual displacement of oil by natural gas and a slow but perceptible emergence of solar and wind power in Saudi Arabia’s grid.

FIGURE 9 SHARE OF ELECTRICITY PRODUCTION IN SAUDI ARABIA [14]

2.2.2 Existing Power Grid

The configuration of Saudi Arabia’s generation fleet, shown in figure 10, remains dominated by conventional thermal technologies, with gas turbines constituting by far the largest cohort of units. Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority (SERA) shows Data for 2019-2023 which reveal that the number of operating gas-turbine units stood at just over 400 throughout the period, accounting for roughly 60 % of all installed machines and underscoring the central role of gas-fired simple-cycle technology in meeting peak and mid-merit demand [5]. Steam turbines formed the second-largest category, rising from 123 units in 2019 to 151 in 2020 before stabilising around 147–150 units thereafter; these plants are typically associated with older oil-fired facilities and combined heat and power installations [5]. Combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGTs), which offer higher thermal efficiencies through the integration of gas and steam cycles, numbered 121 units in 2019 but fell to 93 in 2020 and remained at about 95 units

thereafter, suggesting a period of rationalisation or replacement [5]. Diesel generator sets, used primarily for off-grid applications and backup power, maintained a small but persistent presence at around 25–26 units across the five-year horizon [5].

Renewable energy units, while still marginal in absolute terms, exhibited the only clear growth trend. From just three units in 2019, the number of solar and wind installations increased steadily to eight by 2023 [5]. This five-year doubling of renewable unit count, although from a low base, signals the early integration of variable renewable resources into the grid. Overall fleet size remained broadly stable, fluctuating between 676 and 688 units [5]. The predominance of gas turbines and steam units implies a generation mix oriented toward dispatchable thermal power, with the nascent renewable cohort indicating an emerging diversification that will necessitate enhanced system flexibility and grid management capabilities in future years.

FIGURE 10 NUMBER OF GENERATION UNITS PER TYPE PER YEAR [5]

Moreover, the distribution of licensed capacity tells a slightly different story. Steam-turbine units, though fewer in number, still provide the single largest block of installed capacity, rising from around 38 GW in 2019 to roughly 44.6 GW by 2023 [5]. Simple-cycle gas turbines contribute about one-third of capacity, increasing modestly from just under 30 GW to about 31.5 GW over the same period [5]. Combined-cycle plants, which are more efficient on a per-unit basis, have seen their aggregate capacity contract from 16.7 GW to about 13.3 GW, consistent with the decline in unit count [5]. Diesel-fired capacity remains negligible at a few hundred megawatts, while renewable energy capacity, largely solar, has grown from about

0.3 GW to more than 1.4 GW [5]. The capacity figures thus reinforce the dominance of steam and gas technologies but highlight a nascent shift toward utility-scale renewables.

FIGURE 11 LICENSES CAPACITY BY UNIT TYPE AND YEAR [5]

Beyond the composition of the generation fleet, system planning must account for the temporal profile of electricity demand. As shown in figure 12, monthly load data from the Kingdom’s principal transmission operator, National Grid (NG), reveal a pronounced seasonal swing. Minimum loads of around 28–32 GW occur in the winter months, while maximum loads climb steadily from about 37 GW in January to more than 70 GW in July and August, reflecting the surge in air-conditioning demand during the summer [5]. Average load follows the same trajectory, rising from the low 30-gigawatt range in the first quarter to roughly 60 GW at the mid-year peak and then easing back toward 40 GW in the autumn [5]. Although these figures represent demand served by a single, although dominant, producer, they illustrate the challenge of balancing a system whose peak load in high summer is more than twice its winter minimum. This variability underscores the need for flexible generation, robust transmission infrastructure and demand-side management to maintain reliability across the annual load cycle.

FIGURE 12 MONTHLY DEMAND VARIATION IN SAUDI ARABIA BY NATIONAL GRID [5]

Saudi Arabia has a wide land area which is considered a challenge for the electrical power network. Transmission planning in Saudi Arabia has evolved to support a geographically dispersed generation fleet and increasingly variable loads. The network is dominated by high-voltage overhead circuits, with underground cables deployed mainly in urban or environmentally sensitive zones. At the top of the voltage hierarchy, 380 kV lines form the backbone of bulk power transfer: approximately 43,687 circuit-kilometres (ckt-km) are in service overhead, complemented by 1,020 circuit-kilometres of underground cable [5]. The 132kV network provides regional sub-transmission and accounts for the next-largest share, with about 24,858 ckt-km overhead and 3,362 ckt-km underground [5]. Medium-voltage transmission at 115 kV and 110 kV are there about 7,383 ckt-km and 5,794 ckt-km of overhead line respectively, alongside 1,509 ckt-km and 3,573 ckt-km of underground cable [5]. Only a small 230 kV segment exists (roughly 4,171 ckt-km overhead and 96 ckt-km underground) [5]. The overall mix reflects a preference for overhead construction at higher voltages, while urban distribution relies more on buried cables.

FIGURE 13 LENGTH OF TRANSMISSION LINES BY VOLTAGE [5]

These domestic investments sit alongside efforts to strengthen cross-border connectivity. Saudi Arabia is upgrading the Gulf Cooperation Council interconnection, which has linked its grid to Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar and the United Arab Emirates, enabling the Al-Fadhili HVDC converter station to exchange up to 1,800 MW of power [15]. Bilateral projects are also under way: a 3 GW HVDC link at 500kV with Egypt is being built with converter stations in Tabuk and Medina in Saudi Arabia and Badr in Egypt, spanning about 1,300 km of overhead line and submarine cable and due to come online in stages from 2025 [16]. A proposed interconnection with Iraq would use a 400 kV, 435 km line to exchange up to 1 GW of power[17]. Collectively, these projects aim to enhance regional energy security, facilitate renewable integration and lay the groundwork for a broader Arab electricity market.

2.2.3 Solar Energy

Situated within the global “sun belt”, Saudi Arabia enjoys solar resources that are markedly superior to those of most high-potential regions. Empirical data indicate an average 8.9 hours of sunshine per day, underscoring the prevalence of clear skies and minimal cloud cover across the Kingdom’s arid expanse [18]. On a daily basis the average horizontal solar radiation reaches about 5,600 Wh/m², or 5.6 kWh/m², which integrates to approximately 2,000 kWh/m² per year [18]. This sustained insolation is accompanied by average power levels on the order of 250 W/m², noticeably higher than the 100–200 W/m² typically recorded in other reputedly high-quality solar sites worldwide [18]. Collectively, the long duration of sunlight, high daily energy yield and elevated irradiance illustrate why Saudi Arabia is frequently characterised as a prime environment for photovoltaic development. From a theoretical standpoint, these metrics imply not only ample prospective output per unit area but also a high degree of predictability in the temporal distribution of solar energy, both of which are essential attributes

for planning and financing utility-scale renewable projects within the context of a low-carbon energy transition.

Solar project development in Saudi Arabia began with the Sakaka PV plant, commissioned in 2020 with a capacity of 300 MW. This flagship project demonstrated the feasibility of utility-scale PV within the Saudi grid and used single-axis tracking systems to boost yield by up to 20% compared to fixed-tilt modules [11]. Since then, the solar project pipeline has expanded significantly, both in terms of capacity and geographic distribution. Key installations include the 1.5 GW Sudair project, boasting over 30 km² of bifacial modules and delivering clean energy to nearly 185,000 households, and the 2.06 GW Shuaibah 2 plant, which was contracted in 2022 [11].

The increase in solar PV capacity is also being accompanied by investment in grid infrastructure, including transmission upgrades and smart substations, to handle intermittent output and avoid congestion during peak output hours. Table 1 below gives a view on the currently installed solar plants in Saudi Arabia as of 2025. Solar projects are shown in yellow in Figure 7, with visual indicators for project status and scale.

2.2.4 Wind Energy

Saudi Arabia's onshore wind profile is commercially attractive, with mean wind speeds generally between 6 m/s and 8 m/s and extensive tracts consistently exceeding the 7 m/s threshold that defines economic viability [18]. Although the country's renewable energy strategy is likely to be dominated by solar photovoltaics, wind power makes a valuable contribution by delivering output during periods when solar generation falls off. This temporal complementarity enhances grid stability and underscores the role of wind as a supporting, yet important, component of the Kingdom's low-carbon energy portfolio.

The Dumat AlJandal wind project, commissioned in 2022 with a capacity of 400 MW, marked the country's first utility-scale turbine installation and is projected to offset over 880,000 tons of CO₂ annually [11]. Following this, the Kingdom has advanced other major wind initiatives under National Renewable Energy Program NREP, including Waad Al Shammal, Shaqra, Dwadmi, Starah, and Al Ghat. These projects together add more than 5.5 GW of potential wind capacity to the 2030 target and signal a deliberate effort to map wind-rich territories and scale up supply chains [11].

Among these, the Al Ghat (600 MW) and Waad Al Shammal (500 MW) wind farms stand out as strategic benchmarks in scale and system cost, reinforcing the country's broader ambition to diversify its energy mix with high-capacity and cost-effectiveness. Their award under NREP Round 4 also demonstrated Saudi Arabia's ability to attract highly competitive bids from global developers [11].

Wind power development in Saudi Arabia faces logistical and technical constraints, including turbine import dependency on major European manufacturers, transportation challenges across vast deserts, and more stringent siting requirements due to local topography and legacy land-use rights. Wind projects are shown in blue in Figure 7, with visual indicators for project status and scale.

2.2.5 Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE)

The Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is a key financial metric used to evaluate the economic viability of different generation technologies. It measures the average lifetime cost of producing electricity, normalized per kilowatt-hour, and incorporates capital investment, operational and maintenance expenses, financing terms, and, when relevant, fuel costs. By comparing LCOE values across technologies and regions, policymakers and investors can benchmark projects, tender competitively, and assess trade-offs in system design.

To put it simply, LCOE represents the price at which electricity must be sold for a project to break even over its operational lifetime. It is commonly used in tendering processes and feasibility studies to compare different generation options on a consistent cost basis. For more accurate project modelling, a time-discounted version of the LCOE formula is typically applied [19]:

$$LCOE = \frac{LCC}{E} \quad (1)$$

Where E is electricity generated in grid, and LCC is as shown below [20].

$$LCC = C_{capital} + C_{O\&M} + C_{Replacement} + C_{Salvage} \quad (2)$$

Where; $C_{Capital}$ is the capital cost, $C_{O\&M}$ defines the operation and maintenance cost including fuel and variable and fixed costs (VOM & FOM) if applicable, $C_{Replacement}$ refers to replacement cost and $C_{Salvage}$ is the salvage cost [20]. And LCOE equation can be represented as below:

$$LCOE = \frac{C_{capital} \times CRF + C_{O\&M} + \frac{F}{efficiency\%}}{CF \times 8760} \quad (3)$$

Where CRF is Capital Recovery Factor $= \frac{r(1+r)^n}{(1+r)^n - 1}$, as n is the number of years, and r is discount rate. While CF is the capacity factor.

In Saudi Arabia, most of the LCOE values reported in public sources are based on projected values submitted by developers during competitive bidding rounds. These figures are calculated based on each bidder's financial and technical assumptions and are typically announced after signing the Power Purchase Agreement (PPA). While they do not reflect actual cash flows or measured output, they are reviewed and validated by the procuring authority, making them reliable indicators for policy and planning purposes.

In recent years, these projected LCOE values for solar PV projects in Saudi Arabia have shown a notable decline. Early installations, such as Sakaka, recorded an LCOE of 2.34 ¢/kWh [11]. In contrast, more recent large-scale projects like Sudair, Bisha, and Afif 2 have achieved values as low as 1.23 to 1.28 ¢/kWh [11]. This downward trajectory reflects a combination of factors including falling global module prices, competitive financing facilitated by state-backed banks, economies of scale, and optimized supply chains achieved through tender-based deployment platforms.

Wind projects have also achieved competitive cost levels, although generally higher than solar. Dumat Al-Jandal was tendered at 2.13 ¢/kWh and closed financially near 1.99 ¢/kWh, demonstrating rapid cost recovery under favourable wind conditions [11]. More recent projects such as Shaqra and Starah are estimated in the range of 1.86 to 2.05 ¢/kWh, which already competes with natural gas plants when carbon pricing is considered [11]. Notably, the lowest onshore wind LCOEs globally were recorded in Saudi Arabia, with Al Ghat reaching 1.56558 ¢/kWh and Waad Al Shammal awarded at 1.70187 ¢/kWh, both under NREP Round 4 [11]. These results underscore the Kingdom's success in leveraging large-scale procurement and competitive auctions to drive down renewable costs [11][21].

These values place Saudi Arabia among the most cost-competitive renewable energy markets in the world, with renewable LCOEs now rivaling or undercutting traditional oil-fired generation, even without subsidies[21]. The ongoing reduction in LCOE for both solar and

wind technologies not only enhances the economic feasibility of renewable integration but also strengthens the case for accelerating the transition to a low-carbon energy system.

Table 1, shows a comprehensive list of all installed renewable resources in the kingdom as of August 2025 summing up to reach 9.2 GW. A detailed breakdown of all projects in all stages: installed, underdevelopment, and tendered, is provided in Appendix A, which includes commissioning timelines, capacities, and LCOE.

TABLE 1 INSTALLED RENEWABLE PROJECTS AS OF AUGUST 2025 IN SAUDI ARABIA [11]

Project Name	Status	Year of Commissioning	Type	Capacity (GW)	LCOE cents/kWh
<i>Sakaka</i>	Installed	2020	Solar	0.3	2.3417
<i>Dumat Al-Jandal</i>	Installed	2022	Wind	0.4	2.13
<i>Rabigh 1</i>	Installed	2023	Solar	0.3	1.7016368
<i>Jeddah</i>	Installed	2023	Solar	0.3	1.624112
<i>Sudair</i>	Installed	2023	Solar	1.5	1.239
<i>Layla</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.091	2.98
<i>Saad 1</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.3	1.48267
<i>Shuaibah 1</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.6	1.04
<i>Ar Rass 1</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.7	1.49867
<i>Shuaibah 2</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	2.06	1.79
<i>Saad 2</i>	Installed	2025	Solar	1.125	1.792
<i>Wadi Aldawaser</i>	Installed	2025	Solar	0.112	1.87
<i>Kahfah</i>	Installed	2025	Solar	1.425	1.768

2.3 Problem Statement

The preceding sections highlight the scale of the challenge facing Saudi Arabia’s power sector. power sector emits roughly 260 million tonnes of CO₂ each year, while more than nine-tenths of installed capacity comes from gas and oil plants. Yet national policy now calls for half of all electricity to be supplied from renewables by 2030, implying the addition of about 130 GW of new clean capacity dispatching roughly 58 GW, and the Saudi Green Initiative targets a reduction of 278 Mt CO₂ per annum by that date. Given the Kingdom’s vast geography, rapidly growing demand and entrenched reliance on fossil fuels, meeting these targets will require not only massive deployment of solar and wind but also solutions to manage their intermittency and ensure system reliability. This thesis therefore asks whether Saudi Arabia can feasibly

achieve its 2030 renewable goals and emissions reductions through an optimally designed power system, and what mix of technologies, solar, wind, and carbon capture will be necessary to do so.

Chapter 3: National Potential and Technology Assessment

3.1 General Renewable Resource Assessment

The Ministry of Investment, in its brochure, has described Saudi Arabia's being "naturally endowed" with renewable energy sources, particularly solar and wind [18]. The brochure shows that Saudi Arabia enjoys an average of 8.9 hr a day of sunshine, and an average of horizontal irradiation of 5.6 kWh/m²/day with average irradiance of 250 w/m² exceeding global irradiance average of 100-200 w/m² [18]. Also, the brochure shows that the annual average wind speed in Saudi Arabia reaches 6.0 – 8.0 m/s [18].

Saudi Arabia has a vast land area, with different topography and different landscape. In this section, multiple resources will be used to assess the solar and wind potential in the country in order to evaluate the deployment feasibility of renewable energy sources in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

3.1.1 Solar Irradiation Potential

For PV applications, the Global Horizontal Irradiation is being considered, and since Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) systems is not considered in the thesis, Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI) is not used. Data insight from King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Centre (KASARC), shown in figure 14, shared an annual average global horizontal irradiation (GHI) over five years, from 2013 to 2017, studies over five regions in Saudi Arabia; west, east, north, and south [22]. The figure below shows the global horizontal irradiation in Saudi Arabia can go up to an approximate average of 2,2300 kWh/m² for a year, while the lowest GHI average for a year was in the eastern region which was around 2000 kWh/m² indicating that eastern region gets lower global horizontal irradiation amongst other regions in Saudi Arabia [22].

FIGURE 14 ANNUAL AVERAGE OF GLOBAL HORIZONTAL IRRADIATION (GHI) IN SAUDI ARABIA [22]

More recent data from World Bank Group, using their SOLARGIS tool, shows a map of the average GHI all over the country's map in kWh/m², as shown in figure 15 A, as well as photovoltaic power potential in kWh/kWp shown in figure 15 B [23], it is suggested that 1 kWp of standard module with 16% efficiency takes up to 6.25 m² and more efficient modules with efficiency of 20% uses 5 m², hence an X kWh/m² is nearly equal to Y kWh/kWp neglecting losses [24].

FIGURE 15 A) GLOBAL HORIZONTAL IRRADIATION (GHI) IN SAUDI ARABIA. B) PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER POTENTIAL IN SAUDI ARABIA [23].

Figure 15 A shows that yearly GHI in Saudi Arabia vary over locations, very few regions have a fewer GHI of around 2100 kWh/m², while other locations near Tabuk in the north-western region, near Khamis Mushayt in Asir province, and few locations in central region have high GHI with around 2300 kWh/m² [23]. Figure 15 B shows a relatively similar profile with higher potential across the western parts than eastern. Therefore, solar potential in Saudi Arabia is high, and papers show that the cost of electricity produced by photovoltaic was projected to decrease by 59% compared to 2015 in Saudi Arabia [20].

For region-specific studies, Tabuk is selected, due its high solar potential, to assess its global horizontal irradiation GHI profile using three different methods and sources;

- 1- Meteonorm software,
- 2- King Abdullah for Atomic and Renewable Energy (KACARE) Atlas tool [25],
- 3- and a self-developed python model through a coursework in ET MPhil [26].

TABLE 2 COMPARISON BETWEEN DIFFERENT DATA SOURCES USED AGAINST A PYTHON COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

Value in kWh/m²	Meteonorm	KACARE Tool [25]	Python-Modelled
<i>Daily Average GHI</i>	6.3	6.21	4.9
<i>Monthly Average GHI</i>	191	186.4	149.7
<i>Yearly Total GHI</i>	2292	2236.8	1796.9

The modelled results for Tabuk's solar irradiation are compared against data from Meteonorm and KACARE in Table 2. The modeled results for Tabuk's solar irradiation closely align with data from Meteonorm and KACARE, with slight discrepancies attributed to differences in modeling assumptions, such as clearness index values, diffuse irradiation fractions, and extraterrestrial solar radiation as described in the equation below:

$$GHI = k_t \times H_o \quad (4)$$

Where k_t is the clearness index and H_o is the extraterrestrial solar radiation. The clearness index values for the python computational model is obtained from a literature of an existing study of Tabuk's solar potential, see Appendices C [27]. GHI is also calculated using the below equation

$$GHI = DNI \times \cos(\theta_z) + DHI \quad (5)$$

Where GHI is the global horizontal irradiation, θ_z is the Solar Zenith Angle (angle between the sun and the vertical), DNI is the direct normal irradiation, and DHI is the diffuse horizontal irradiance.

3.1.2 Wind Speed Potential

In the context of renewable energy, Saudi Arabia's solar potential stands out as the most significant resource. Nonetheless, with recent renewable projects expansions among the country's vision, wind energy is also being studied and increasingly considered. There are many literatures that studies the wind speed profile across the country with the use of King Abdullah City for Atomic and Renewable Energy (KACARE) Atlas tool [25].

FIGURE 16 AVERAGE WIND SPEED ACROSS SAUDI ARABIA [28]

The map in figure 16 shows various levels of wind speed all over the country with average between 6.0 to 8.0 m/s [28]. Some areas around the east coast, central region, and western region have a higher average of 7.5 to 8.0 m/s, while southwestern region beside the red sea records amongst the lowest region with wind speed average of around 4.0 to 5.0 m/s [28]. KACARE has deployed multiple wind speed monitoring station across the kingdom to assess the data through their Renewable Resources Atlas tool [25]. Figure 17 below shows average wind speed across six different monitoring stations.

FIGURE 17 MONTHLY AVERAGE WIND SPEED IN 2016 IN DIFFERENT LOCATIONS WITH THE COUNTRY [25]

Saudi Arabia has several locations that are suitable for wind farms, making the country a promising place to harvest those wind capabilities along with its solar potential. As of 2025, as mentioned earlier, Saudi Arabia has already planned for several wind projects and installed some, appendices A shows the full details of planned wind projects.

3.2 Emerging Low-Carbon Technologies

3.2.1 Carbon Management

Saudi Arabia ranks amongst the highest ten countries globally with CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion, with an annual emission of 533 MtCO₂[12]. There is a lot to do in the coming years in order for the country to meet its national objectives and enhance its progress towards the commitment under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and Paris Agreement goals [10][29]. Therefore, the country has pledged to reach climate neutrality by 2060 and 278 Mtpa reduction of CO₂ by 2030, so the country has planned many projects to support those objectives including the increase of renewable shares part of the power mix to 50% by 2030 [7].

Saudi Green Initiative, announced in 2021, has laid the foundation for Saudi Arabia path towards a greener future [8]. The initiative included multiple programs such as reducing emissions, greening Saudi, and land and sea protection [8]. SGI's emission reductions plans include multiple pathways; carbon management, renewable energy, hydrogen investment, energy efficiency, and waste management [7]. As part of carbon management, a circular carbon economy (CCE) framework has been established aiming at reducing, reusing, recycling, and removing CO₂ emissions through advanced technologies such as direct air capture (DAC)

systems and carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS) systems, CCE framework was initiated to fill the gap and promote innovation in the context of carbon management [7].

Carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) combines two main approaches, which are; 1- carbon capture and storage (CCS), which permanently stores CO₂ emissions underground, and 2- carbon capture and utilization (CCU), where CO₂ is used in industrial applications, either stored in materials such as concrete or released later through synthetic fuel production [30]. In Saudi Arabia, CCUS is central to the circular carbon economy (CCE) framework, hence, the kingdom has invested in CO₂-enhanced oil recovery and large-scale capture and utilization projects, aligning with global clean energy initiatives, as current capacity stands at 0.8 million tons per year through the Uthmaniyah project, with two more projects of 2.8 Mt per year each expected by 2027–2028 [30]. Saudi Arabia has announced a phased approach, targeting 9 Mt per year by 2027–2028 and scaling to 44 Mt per year by 2035 and planning to transform Jubail and Yanbu cities as global hubs for CCUS [30][29].

FIGURE 18 CARBON CAPTURE AND STORAGE (CCS) READINESS INDEX SCORE [31]

The carbon capture and storage (CCS) Index in figure 18 reveals a strong link between supportive policy environments and large-scale CCS deployment, showing top-ranking nations and developing countries position for CCS. Saudi Arabia stands in a mid-range position, with strong geological storage potential but only moderate progress on regulatory and legal frameworks [31]. While the Kingdom has been able to advance CCS deployment through its

governance approach, this progress has relied on fewer policy measures than typically required in other jurisdictions, which contributes to its relatively lower CCS Policy Index score [31].

3.2.2 Green Hydrogen

Saudi Arabia is heavily investing in economy diversification and due to the strong renewables' potential of the Kingdom, Saudi Arabia is planning to utilise the renewable energy as an enabler to become a global leader in green hydrogen production through national champions such as NEOM and Aramco. The Public Investment Fund of Saudi Arabia has committed to invest 10B USD in the production of green hydrogen [32]. The country has already initiated a giga project in Neom known as NEOM Green Hydrogen Project which is under development and it will be powered with 4GW of renewable from solar and wind, and will have the capacity to produce 250,000 tons of green hydrogen annually by 2026 and 1.2 million tons per year of green ammonia [7][29]. Figure 19 below gives an overview of NEOM green hydrogen production [10].

FIGURE 19 GREEN HYDROGEN PRODUCTION IN NEOM, SAUDI ARABIA [10]

3.2.3 Battery Energy Storage System (BESS)

In order to enhance grid stability as renewable energy is projected to reach 50% of the power mix in 2030, an energy storage system has to be established to accommodate that. The country is aiming at reaching a battery energy storage system (BESS) of around 48 GWh by 2030 to better utilise the renewable energy sources [33][34].

Saudi Arabia has announced four gigantic BESS projects to be completed in 2025, each of them with a capacity of 2.6 GWh, and are located in Bisha, Najran, Khamis Mushayt/Asir, and Jazan/Madaya, with Bisha's already connected to grid [35][36]. As shown in Table 3, in order

to reach the main BESS target, a pipeline of BESS project is undergoing targeting to reach 33.5 GWh by 2027, 25.5 GWh are under construction with cut-off year in 2026, and the remainder is at tendering stage, with planned projects with a size of 34 GWh to be completed by end of 2030. This pipeline is carried out by big energy companies in the country such as Saudi Electricity Company (SEC), Saudi Power Procurement Company (SPPC), also known as principal buyer, NEOM, and Red Sea Global [35][37][38][39][40]. With that, Saudi Arabia shows a real dedication towards accomplishing its objectives in line with its goal of achieving net-zero by 2060. Table 3 below shows the year to date announced projects in detail.

TABLE 3 PROJECT PIPELINE OF BESS PROJECTS IN SAUDI ARABIA BY 2027 [36][35][37][38][39][41][40].

Project	Size in MWh	Company	Cut-off Year (Status)
<i>Bisha</i>	2600	SEC	2025(operational)
<i>Najran</i>	2600	SEC	2025(construction)
<i>Khamis Mushayt/Asir</i>	2600	SEC	2025(construction)
<i>Madaya/Jazan</i>	2600	SEC	2025(construction)
<i>Riyadh</i>	2500	SEC	2026(construction)
<i>Qaisumah</i>	2500	SEC	2026(construction)
<i>Dawadmi</i>	2500	SEC	2026(construction)
<i>AlJouf</i>	2500	SEC	2026(construction)
<i>Rabigh</i>	2500	SEC	2026(construction)
<i>NEOM</i>	600	NEOM Green Hydrogen Company	(construction)
<i>Red Sea Project</i>	1300	Red Sea Global	(operational)
<i>Amaala Project</i>	760	Red Sea Global	(construction)
<i>Al-Muwaih</i>	2000	SPPC	2027(tendering)
<i>Haden</i>	2000	SPPC	2027(tendering)
<i>Khushaybi</i>	2000	SPPC	2027(tendering)
<i>Kahafa</i>	2000	SPPC	2027(tendering)
<i>Upcoming Planned</i>	34000	SPPC	2030(planning)

3.3 Economic Implications

The economic side of the energy transition in Saudi Arabia carries both opportunities and challenges. The government has already allocated around \$187 billion to support climate goals by 2030, aiming to reduce reliance on oil and move strongly toward renewable energy [10]. Renewables can bring large economic benefits, where the sector could generate between \$40–\$60 billion in revenues, add around 137,000 new jobs, and contribute about \$51 billion to the national GDP [42]. However, these positive prospects, come with the challenge of very high

upfront capital costs, especially for technologies that require large-scale deployment, and the fact that traditional fossil fuel-dependent system may experience an economic impact during the transition. Another important economic factor that shapes this transition is the role of domestic fuel subsidies, which influence the relative competitiveness of renewables compared to conventional energy sources.

A paper assessing the techno-economic potential of Saudi Arabia by Alyahya [43], has included a comparison of the fuel subsidies in Saudi Arabia with other neighbouring countries such as Egypt, Kuwait, and UAE. Table 4 clearly shows that offered subsidies have led to low costs affecting the national economy, where Saudi Arabia’s average subsidisation rate reached to almost 80% [43]. However, this won’t last longer, especially with the increasing carbon pricing globally, and the efforts being done in the country to raise the renewables contribution, that should provide some alternatives where those money can be used in the development of cleaner projects in line with the Kingdom’s vision.

TABLE 4 ENERGY SUBSIDIES IN SAUDI ARABIA COMPARED WITH NEIGHBOURING COUNTRIES [43].

Country	Average Subsidisation rate (%)	Subsidy (USD/Person)	Subsidy by Fuel (Billion USD)			
			Oil	Gas	Electricity	Total
<i>Saudi Arabia</i>	79.5	2291	46.1	0.0	14.8	60.9
<i>Kuwait</i>	87.8	3729	4.3	2.1	4.7	11.1
<i>UAE</i>	69.1	4172	3.9	11.5	6.4	21.8
<i>Egypt</i>	54.2	296	15.3	3.8	5.4	24.5

An evaluation of costs across generation and storage is central to understanding how Saudi Arabia can balance the high investments needed today with the long-term diversification gains expected in the future. A research is done to collect the average LCOE of each power generation technology/fuel and conduct a comparative assessment including their emissions factor per energy produced as shown in the table below.

There are almost no papers stating the approximate LCOE for natural gas in the power generation, however a paper has been found which provides input data to estimate LCOE [44]. Therefore, this data is used in this thesis to approximately estimate the LCOE for gas power as shown in equations 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9. Input data is converted into cents/kWh where applicable, the paper estimated the following; discount rate $r=5\%$, CAPEX=1,014 \$/kW, variable

O&M=0.27 cents/kWh, fixed O&M=29.435 \$/kW, and fuel cost=3.16-8.28 cents/kWh [44], assuming span life of 30 years and a capacity factor (CF) of 60%.

$$CRF = \frac{r(1+r)^n}{(1+r)^n - 1} = \frac{0.05(1+0.05)^{30}}{(1+0.05)^{30} - 1} = 0.06505 \quad (6)$$

Where CRF is the capital recovery factor.

$$CAPEX_{Annualised} = 1014 \times 0.06505 = 65.9\$ = 0.659 \text{ cents} \quad (7)$$

$$CAPEX_{electricity} = \frac{CAPEX_{Annualised}}{CF \times 8760} = \frac{0.659}{0.60 \times 8760} = 1.26 \text{ cents/kWh} \quad (8)$$

$$Oper. Maint_{Fixed} = \frac{29.435}{CF \times 8760} = \frac{29.435}{0.60 \times 8760} = 0.56 \text{ cents/kWh} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} LCOE_{By GAS} &= CAPEX_{electricity} + Oper. Maint_{Fixed} + Oper. Maint_{Var} + Fuel Cost \\ &= 1.26 + 0.56 + 0.27 + \frac{3.16 + 8.28}{2} \cong 7.81 \text{ cents/kWh} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

TABLE 5 LCOE COMPARISON BETWEEN DIFFERENT POWER GENERATION TECHNOLOGIES [45][44][46].

Generation source	CO ₂ at median intensity 50% (kg CO ₂ eq/MWh)**	LCOE (cents/kWh)
<i>Solar PV</i>	46	~1.61*
<i>Wind Energy</i>	12	~1.84*
<i>Natural Gas</i>	469	~7.81
<i>Oil</i>	54.2	10-16

*LCOEs for Solar and Wind are using the average LCOEs for all installed and under development projects in Saudi shown in Table 1.

** CO₂eq is estimated considering a Life Cycle Assessment LCA [45].

Table 5 shows the impact of significant evolvement in renewable energy in the past decades as it reaches LCOE way less than conventional resources, yet, due to the variability and intermittency of renewables, the costs of storage and backup supplies could raise the effective system cost. It is worth to mention that natural gas power LCOE is expected to be higher in many other regions, however the calculated LCOE for gas power shown in the table is using data considering the subsidisation in the country [44]. The LCOE data for PV system in the table is taken from the announced values shown in table 1, however papers have indicated that the average LCOE for a PV system could reach about 5.33 cents/kWh, indicating that PV system outperforms CSP system in terms of system costs, that also impacted the green hydrogen production as the levelised cost of hydrogen (LCOH) production is lower for the PV system at 4.23 \$/kgH₂ [47]. BESS systems play a significant role in systems cost, it is found that, as of 2024, the levelised cost of storage (LCOS) of a li-ion BESS has declined to 30-40

cents/kWh, reduced by around 80% over the last decade, making it a bit higher than hydro pump technology and lower than vanadium-flow BESS technology [48].

Chapter 4: Methodology

This chapter discusses the methodology followed upon selecting the suitable open-source energy modelling tool, and the procedures used to meet the objectives as stipulated in Chapter 1, Section 1.2. The main objective of this thesis is to develop a power systems model in Saudi Arabia meeting its ambition of reducing CO₂ emissions and displacing liquid fuel from the power mix by 2030.

4.1 Tools and Software Used

Energy system modelling (ESM) involves creating computer-based representations of entire energy systems including spanning electricity, heating, transport, industry, and other sectors, to analyse their performance and interactions. Such models capture flows between primary energy sources, energy carriers, and end-use sectors, allowing researchers and policymakers to assess technological options, resource efficiency, and environmental impacts. ESM can be applied at multiple scales, from global to local, and over various time horizons, from hourly dispatch to multi-decade transition pathways.

A key strength of ESM lies in its ability to evaluate integrated, cross-sector scenarios, which is essential for countries with large geographic areas, diverse energy resources, and ambitious transition targets. These tools help explore how different mixes of generation, storage, and transmission infrastructure can meet demand reliably while achieving cost and emissions objectives.

In recent years, model development has accelerated, driven in part by the need to address challenges associated with integrating variable renewable energy sources (VRES) [49]. New tools and advanced features have emerged, moving beyond sector-specific studies to provide a broader, state-of-the-art overview of capabilities. This expanded scope enables analysts to select models that can robustly address the technical, economic, and operational complexities of modern energy systems [49].

4.1.1 Energy Modelling Tools Analysis

This subsection draws on insights from papers assessing and comparing the most recent energy modelling tools. A comprehensive review of over 70 energy and electricity modelling tools conducted by [49]. The reviewed work offers an overview of model capabilities, covering general logic, spatiotemporal resolution, and technological and economic features. By

consolidating diverse approaches, from short-term power system analysis to long-term global models, it provides valuable context for selecting a suitable tool to assess Saudi Arabia's renewable integration objectives in this thesis.

With Saudi Arabia targeting 50% of electricity generation from renewables by 2030, modelling the power and electrical system requires capturing those pathways and assessing its operational dynamics. High shares of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) introduce challenges that occur at very short timescales including reduced system inertia, higher curtailment, faster frequency changes, and limits in reactive power capability. These stability services such as frequency and voltage regulation, spinning reserve, and system restoration, have traditionally been delivered by conventional fossil-fuelled plants. In a low-carbon system, they must increasingly be provided by renewables or supporting technologies, although limited, such as batteries, advanced wind turbine configurations, and utility-scale PV systems with grid support capabilities.

Energy system models can be categorised by approach and methodology. Broadly, the bottom-up (engineering) approach describes technologies in detail, while the top-down (economic) approach captures macroeconomic interactions, hybrid approaches combine both [49]. Methodologies include three types of models, which are simulation models, optimisation models, and equilibrium models [49]. Simulation models test predefined system configurations, while optimisation models determine cost- or performance-optimal solutions under constraints, using techniques such as linear or mixed-integer programming, and equilibrium models represent market behaviour either across the whole economy (general equilibrium) or within specific sectors (partial equilibrium) [49]. For renewable integration studies, bottom-up optimisation models are often preferred, as they capture both technical characteristics and operational constraints of the power system [49]. Hence, in this thesis we are narrowing the options that have a bottom-up approach which will be compared and analysed.

According to [49], in the **General logic** section, energy and electricity models are typically designed with purposes that can be grouped into four main categories. Power System Analysis Tools (PSAT) which focus on detailed technical studies such as power flows, dynamic stability, and fault analysis. Operation Decision Support (ODS) models optimise system dispatch and operation over short-term horizons, typically at national or regional scales. Investment Decision Support (IDS) models guide long-term capacity planning, using either a perfect

foresight approach, optimising the entire study period with full knowledge of future conditions, or a near-sighted approach, which plans sequentially based on current data. Finally, Scenario (S) tools explore long-term pathways under different assumptions, such as policy changes, technology adoption, or demand evolution [49].

An important factor to consider when assessing energy modelling tools is their **spatiotemporal resolution** [49]. This defines both the temporal granularity and the geographic scope of analysis, influencing how well variability in high-VRES systems is represented and sets limitations to which processes can be appropriately modelled [49]. Accurate resolution is crucial for capturing network constraints, regional interactions, and dynamic system behaviour across different operational and planning horizons.

A crucial step in selecting an appropriate modelling framework is understanding the range of **technological and economic parameters** that determine system behaviour [49]. As illustrated in Figure 14, models can incorporate a diverse set of components to capture the complexities of integrating large shares of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) [49]. These include conventional generation, renewable generation technologies, and energy storage solutions. Grid representation varies in complexity, from detailed AC power flow to simplified net transfer capacity approaches, each with implications for computational requirements and accuracy. Models may also include multi-commodity interactions (electricity, heat, hydrogen) and sectoral demand profiles for buildings, transport, and industry [49]. Demand elasticity and demand side management, including demand response, are increasingly relevant for balancing intermittent supply [49]. Cost parameters (e.g. capital, O&M, fuel, CO₂ pricing) and market structure assumptions further shape system outcomes. Finally, emission modelling enables assessment of environmental impacts. Understanding how each of these factors is represented within a model is critical to ensuring that the selected tool can adequately address the operational and investment challenges posed by Saudi Arabia's 2030 renewable energy and decarbonisation targets.

FIGURE 20 FLOWCHART ILLUSTRATING THE MODELLING TOOL SELECTION [49]

After choosing the selection criteria for the most suitable modelling tools, a comparison of four open-source modelling tools, among the 75 energy models, is conducted, which are Calliope, OSeMOSYS, PLEXOS, and PyPSA. Comparison is based on the approach presented in the paper [49], which followed the main requirement needed to assess electricity systems with large shared of variable renewable energy resources (VRES) discussed in the preceding paragraphs of this section, which are:

- 1- The general logic; the purpose,
- 2- the spatiotemporal resolution,
- 3- the technological and economic parameters, and
- 4- other factors such as the used software, approach, and geographical coverage.

Table 6 below shows the comparison, and the full list of 75 energy modelling tools comparison can be found in appendix B.1.

TABLE 6 COMPARISON BETWEEN FOUR OF THE TARGETED MODELLING TOOLS IN THE THESIS [49]

	<i>Calliope</i> (#3)	<i>OSeMOSYS</i> (#48)	<i>PLEXOS</i> (#49)	<i>PyPSA</i> (#54)
Availability (AV)	Open Source	Open Source	Commercial	Open Source
Software Purpose	Python I & ODS	GNU MathProg IDS	Stand-alone I & ODS, S, PSAT	Python I & ODS, PSAT
Approach (Appr.)	Bottom-Up	Bottom-Up	Bottom-Up	Bottom-Up
Methodology	LinearProg (MIP under development)	LinearProg	LinearProg	LinearProg
Temporal resolution	User Defined	User Defined (intra-annual)	User Defined up to 1 min (usually hourly)	User Defined (Hourly)
Modelling horizon	User Defined	User Defined (10-100 years)	User Defined (1 day to 50+ years)	1 year
Geographical coverage	User Defined	Community - Continental	Single project - Global	Local - Continental
Conventional generation	All	All	All	All
Renewable generation	All	All	All	All
Storage	All	All	All (Generic)	All (Generic)
Grid	Net Transfer Capacity	None	None (per paper)	Non-linear/Linear Power Flow; Net Transfer Capacity
Commodities	Electricity, Hydrogen, Heat & Fuels	Electricity	Electricity (with Heat), Gas & Water	Any commodity
Demand sectors	Aggregated	Aggregated	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Aggregated
Demand elasticity	Inelastic	Inelastic	Elastic	Inelastic
Demand response	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Costs	I, O&M, Fuel, CO2	I, O&M, Fuel, CO2, Balancing cost	I, O&M, Fuel, CO2, Balancing cost	Capital Cost & Marginal Cost
Market Emissions	Supply/Demand Any pollutant	Supply/Demand Any pollutant	None (per paper) All (Generic)	Supply/Demand CO2

Table 6 depicts the capabilities of the four tools; Calliope, OSeMOYSYS, PLEXOS, and PyPSA. In terms of modelling horizons, all tools fit for the thesis study as it simulates the power system in Saudi Arabia in 2030. PyPSA has the capability of accommodating any type of commodities. Also, PyPSA and PLEXOS, unlike the others, can focus on detailed power studies including power flow and stability as they are Power Systems Analysis Tools (PSAT). In contrast, PLEXOS is not an open-source tool, which require some sort of payment, and consequently open-source and free tools has really expanded, and the only open-source tool in

the comparison that has PSAT is PyPSA, while Calliope and OSeMOSYS are focusing on investment and operation decision support-modelling type. PLEXOS's grid capabilities lack non-linear power flow. On the contrary, PyPSA features many grid capabilities, such as non-linear/linear power flow and net transfer capacity.

Another paper has conducted a study of 20 energy modelling tools [50]. Selected features for a selection of different software tools are compared in appendix B.2, Appendix B.2 shows an overview of those 20 modelling tools in relation to PyPSA's features. For thorough power systems modelling PyPSA offers more detailed modelling of power systems by incorporating the physics of power flow based on network impedances, setting it apart from common energy system models like Calliope and OSeMOSYS. While it can represent broader energy networks through link components, it does not yet support certain features such as OSeMOSYS' multi-year dynamic investment [51]. Its capabilities are most comparable to the commercial PLEXOS tool, though, as mentioned before, PLEXOS does not include non-linear power flow. Moreover, PyPSA relies on libraries for optimisation and can work with various solvers, including Gurobi, GLPK, CLP/CBC, and the developing open-source solver HiGHS [51]. For this thesis, PyPSA was chosen for its ability to model national-scale power networks, through its PyPSA-Earth model, at high spatiotemporal resolution, perform both technical and economic optimisation, and incorporate emissions control. More about PyPSA-Earth model is to be discussed in the next sub-section.

4.1.2 Overview of Python for Power Systems Analysis (PyPSA-Earth)

PyPSA-Earth is an open-source data management and optimisation tool designed to give policymakers, companies, and researchers a common platform for diverse macro-energy system analyses supporting the energy transition [52]. It allows the creation of customised country, continental, or global models within a single code repository, enabling greater collaboration and broader benefits for users [52]. PyPSA-Earth is developed to enable users to conduct many studies, such as energy systems transition studies, power systems studies, technology evaluation, and technology phase-out studies, which suits this thesis's objectives as Saudi Arabia is assessed to achieve its 2030 goals of displacing liquid fuel by renewables in the electricity mix with a share of renewables of 50% [52].

FIGURE 21 PYPSA-EARTH MODEL DESIGN [52]

Figure 15 illustrates the end-to-end PyPSA-Earth process, from data gathering to producing final outputs. PyPSA-Earth activities are segmented into three groups, open data, open energy system model, and open-source solver. First open data activities mainly focus on data collection, creation, prediction, fusion, and modification that applies in several aspects, such as electricity prediction. Data collection stage is categorised into two types, GIS related data and non-GIS. GIS related data are about data associated with a geographical area such as population, wind speed, and solar irradiation. While non-GIS inputs are about general data such as technology cost and specifications and fuel prices. Those data activities work on high spatiotemporal resolution data to provide accurate energy system model solutions [52]. After providing the configuration parameters and countries of interest, data is collected and processed as illustrated and then fed into the framework, in which the open-source solver will find the optimal solution, such as least cost and least emission system. Secondly, the work on open energy system modelling aims to add new capabilities and data flows to the model, including the creation of a sector-coupled framework with multi-horizon optimisation suitable for global applications. Thirdly, efforts related to open-source solvers involve developing benchmarks and improving interfaces to support the use and advancement of these solvers. PyPSA uses both commercial and open-source solvers, such as Gurobi, GLPK, and the developing open-source solver HiGHS [51].

FIGURE 22 DIAGRAM SHOWS A PYPASA-EARTH WORKFLOW WHERE EACH BOX REPRESENTS A RULE THAT PROCESSES INPUTS INTO OUTPUTS. DASHED BOXES ARE COMPLETED STEPS, WHILE SOLID BOXES ARE PENDING TASKS. WITH ONE LINE OF CODE, THE WORKFLOW GENERATES FOUR LEAST-COST SCENARIOS [52]

PyPSA-Earth relies on a workflow management tool called the ‘Snakemake’ which breaks down a large software process into smaller subtasks, called ‘rules’, which are automatically linked together to get the needed output. This method supports sustainable software design by making the work reproducible, adaptable, and transparent, as noted in [52]. In PyPSA-Earth, the full workflow is built as a set of new ‘Snakemake’ rules. As shown in Figure 16, the workflow is generated automatically by ‘Snakemake’, and the user can run any part of it with just one line of code [52]. This makes it easier for both users and developers because complex processes are split into smaller, modular tasks that are simpler to work with and maintain. The ‘Snakemake’ tool can also be used to run different scenarios with multiple networks using ‘solve_all_networks’ code, where wildcards define the spatial resolution (50 or 100 clusters) and temporal resolution (1-hour or 3-hour intervals, labelled as Co2L-1H and Co2L-3H).

4.2 Limitations for Model and Thesis

The author of [52] has highlighted several limitations of the PyPSA-Earth model. One of the main points is that the model is as good as the data it relies on, and because it uses open sources, data quality can be an issue. In many regions, especially outside Europe and North America, there is no public institution providing detailed grid topology with geolocation, which makes modelling less accurate [52]. The paper mentions possible improvements such as using satellite imagery and neural networks to detect infrastructure, which could help fill data gaps [52]. Another limitation is the demand time series [52]. In some low-income countries, predictions are affected by biases in the input data, and in some cases, demand values are missing due to software issues. The authors also note that global open datasets can be too general for national-level studies, so there is a need to integrate more precise local data [52]. On the technology side, PyPSA-Earth does not yet include some generation options like CSP, wave/tidal, or advanced storage [52].

In this thesis, the main limitation came from the availability of detailed and updated energy system data for Saudi Arabia. Compared to other countries, the literature and public datasets covering the Saudi power system are limited. The thesis study relied on public data in government and research websites as well as the default datasets provided within PyPSA-Earth, which are compiled from various open sources and published references, such as cost data for different technologies, which may not reflect the exact situation in Saudi Arabia.

4.3 Approach

In order to satisfy the thesis objectives, there are certain procedures have been followed. As stated earlier in this chapter, the Saudi vision 2030 has been the motivating driver for this thesis, in which we will assess the kingdom's power systems in 2030. Multiple pathways have been developed for that sake. Some technologies were not considered in this thesis, such as CSP. Moreover, in order to simulate the decarbonisation goals of the kingdom, scenarios have been built with the use CO₂ limits. Those models are built to be compared with the country's vision 2030. This thesis will finally provide recommendations for the Saudi power systems of 2030.

PyPSA-Earth repository has been cloned and then it has been run specifically for Saudi Arabia using some instructions in the configuration file. For the run, all work packages have been used and downloaded, which include demand, conventional generators, renewable energy sources, storage units, networks and substations. Worth to mention that not all of the installed

renewables stated in Chapter 2-Table 1 have been included, therefore some amendments on some of the work packages have been done to accommodate that accordingly. Notably, as mentioned before, within the work packages, some data are used as input fed into the framework of PyPSA-Earth such as cost data for various technologies. Configuration files enables the users to make certain scenarios, which include temporal resolution, types of generation fuel to be included, type of generation technologies to be included, CO₂ limit, and so forth. Those data and resources within the work packages are used as inputs to be fed into the framework model and build the network. After that, network is solved and optimized to reach least cost, least emission using one of the aforementioned solvers. In this thesis, GLPK and Gurobi are used as solvers, VS Code as the main terminal software, and Jupyter Lab as the notebook.

4.4 Data Sources and Handling

In this thesis, online governmental dashboards, tracking tools, annual reports, publications, journals, and public webpages have been used to collect data. Published data from Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority (SERA) and King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Centre (KAPSARC) have also been used throughout the thesis for the Saudi energy systems data. Some of those data have been used to modify some of the current data such as the renewable profile in Saudi Arabia as it is progressing fast and the data exist in PyPSA-Earth may not exactly match local conditions.

PyPSA-Earth work packages have some GIS specific and non-GIS specific data, such as conventional power plants, solar irradiation, wind speed, GDP, demand time series, population growth, technology cost, and so forth using open-source references such as Open Street Map, World Bank Group, and IRENA. Those data are used to build the model network, run the optimisation, and analyse the results. Table 7 below shows a glimpse of the data used within the PyPSA-Earth packages, as it shows the technologies cost assumptions including CAPEX, variable operation and maintenance costs (VOM), fixed operation and maintenance costs (FOM), fuel cost, and CO₂ intensity. Those data are used in the thesis to calculate system LCOE and system emissions using a discount rate of 7.1% as per PyPSA-Earth packages.

TABLE 7 PYPSA-EARTH'S DATA FOR SOME OF THE TECHNOLOGIES COSTS AND CO₂ INTENSITIES

Carrier	CAPEX (\$/kW)	Fuel Cost (\$/MWh)	FOM (% of CAPEX)	VOM (\$/MWh)	Thermal Efficiency (%)	Life Time (y)	CO ₂ Intensity (t/MWh)
<i>Solar PV</i>	597.66	0	1.95	0.012		40	0
<i>Onshore Wind</i>	1205.44	0	1.21	1.57		30	0
<i>Natural Gas</i>	966	27.03	3.35	4.89	0.58	25	0.198
<i>Oil</i>	400	58.2	2.46	6.98	0.35	25	0.257

4.5 System Boundaries and Assumptions

The model covers Saudi Arabia's national power system, with a time boundary of 2030 in alignment and with comparison with vision 2030 targets. In PyPSA-Earth configuration file, a temporal resolution of 3 hours is used. Detailed boundaries and assumptions are as follow:

- Simulation is done for the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA)
- Oil is excluded from the energy mix by 2030.
- CSP technology is excluded.
- Gas generation is considered using only the combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) technology as part of the PyPSA-Earth resources in "powerplants.csv".
- Country's renewable profile is based on KAPSARC tracking tool in [11].
- Conventional power plants data in PyPSA-Earth packages has been used.
- Various technologies' cost in PyPSA-Earth packages has been used using 2030 assumptions.
- Demand growth assumption by 2030 is based on PyPSA prediction using its GDP and population growth factors that are based on 2020 data.
- Optimisation increase in power capacity is based on PyPSA-Earth libraries and data.
- CO₂ emissions annual cap target is 77.5 Mt for base scenario and 51.875 Mt for Scenario B.
- Weather data is collected part of PyPSA-Earth using data from 2013.
- Scenarios CO₂ emissions does not include life cycle emissions.
- LCOE calculations for solar is based on a discount rate of 7.1% and life time of 40 years

Chapter 5: Power System Modelling Scenarios

In this chapter, the data used in the work packages of PyPSA-Earth to build the network will be discussed along with the scenarios to be followed. There will be two scenarios all of them assessing the Saudi power network in 2030 in terms of LCOE and CO₂ emissions. PyPSA-Earth data packages has a significant role in shaping the network, optimising the cost and emissions, and providing the result. Hence, prior to delving into the scenarios, some of the highlight data will be mentioned, discussed, and cross-checked with government data.

Table 8 below shows a comparison between PyPSA-Earth data packages and Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority (SERA)'s report [5], for current total power generation capacity, capacities by carrier, and number of power plants in Saudi Arabia. The data used in this thesis is sources from the PyPSA packages, however, these comparison shows the that differences may lead to slight variations in the analysis and simulation outcomes, which will be further discussed in the sensitivity analysis section.

TABLE 8 PYPSA-EARTH'S DATA SERA'S DATA FOR SAUDI POWER PROFILE

	Unit	PyPSA-Earth	SERA's Report [5]
<i>Renewables Power</i>	GW	2.6	1.4
<i>Conventional Power</i>	GW	131.6	89.7
<i>Total Power</i>	GW	134.2	91.1
<i>Number of Power Plants</i>	#	133	91

As presented in the table above, those data show the current capacities of Saudi Arabia, the PyPSA data was collected using the instruction “p_nom” which shows the data before optimisation. In the upcoming scenarios, data for capacities will be presented after optimisation which is recalled using the instruction “p_nom_opt”. Although there is a discrepancy in data, the capacities used are PyPSA's except in scenario B, renewables will be updated to recent data.

GDP and population growth factor are playing a significant role in shaping the demand profile in Saudi Arabia in 2030. Algarei has plotted the demand forecast using PyPSA's embedded-in forecast as shown in figure 23 below, which can give us a clear picture of the generation consumption demand in 2030 for this thesis's scenarios reaching in the figure almost 520-560 TWh [51].

FIGURE 23 PYPASA'S DEMAND GROWTH FORECAST FOR SAUDI ARABIA IN 2030, 2040, AND 2050 [51]

As presented in chapter 1 & 2, Saudi Arabia's fuel combustion emissions has reached 533 Mtpa of CO₂, almost 247 Mtpa of which is from the power generation, and as part of Saudi Green Initiative (SGI) in vision 2030, the country plans to reduce its annual emissions by 278 Mt of CO₂, this value represent the emissions reduction in all sectors with no specifications including the contribution from planting trees. Hence, the remainder of the emissions in 2030 will be almost 255 Mt of CO₂, therefore the power sector CO₂ limits for both scenarios will be done assuming the following:

1. Scenario A will have a CO₂ limit of 30% of 255, which is almost 77.5 Mt.
2. Scenario B, optimistically, will have a CO₂ limit of 51.875 Mt which is around 20% of 255.

Terminologies/ carriers used throughout PyPSA-Earth:

- 1- Solar – Solar PV
- 2- Onwind – Onshore wind
- 3- Offwind-dc – Offshore wind with HVDC connection
- 4- Offwind-ac – Offshore wind with AC connection
- 5- Oil – Oil-fired generation
- 6- CCGT – combined cycle gas turbine which is attributed to gas-fired generation.

5.1 2030 Scenario A (All Technologies)

This scenario was done to simulate the power network of Saudi Arabia in 2030 using its built-in data to examine the model in 2030 including all types of carriers and technologies. The scenario is run using “snakemake_solve_all_networks” role with the following selections

made in the configuration file (config.yaml); 1- 2030 target year, 2- 10 clusters for spatiotemporal resolution, 3- Including all renewable technologies, 4- CO₂ emission cap of 77.5 Mt, 5- Making renewables extendable for optimisation, 6- Weather profile is taken from 2013, 7- Putting “estimate_renewable_capacities: p_nom_max” to false to allow some generations from gas-fired power, and 8- Time step is 3 hours for temporal resolution. Figure 24 below shows the current selection of the above factors.

```

load_options:
  ssp: "ssp2-2.6"
  weather_year: 2013
  prediction_year: 2030
  scale: 1

electricity:
  base_voltage: 380.
  voltages: [132., 220., 300., 380., 500., 750.]
  co2limit: 7.75e+7

extendable_carriers:
  Generator: [solar, onwind, offwind-ac, offwind-dc, OCGT]
  StorageUnit: [] # battery
  Store: [battery, H2]
  Link: [] # H2 p

powerplants_filter: (DateOut >= 2022 or DateOut != DateOut)
custom_powerplants: false # "false" us

conventional_carriers: [nuclear, oil, OCGT, CCGT, coal, lignite, geothermal, biomass]
renewable_carriers: [solar, onwind, offwind-ac, offwind-dc, hydro]

scenario:
  simpl: [""]
  ll: ["copt"]
  clusters: [10]
  opts: [Co2L-3h]
  planning_horizons:
    - 2030

# Costs Configuration
costs:
  year: 2030
  version: v0.12.0
  discontrate: [0.071]

estimate_renewable_capacities:
  stats: "irena"
  year: 2023
  p_nom_min: 1
  p_nom_max: false
  
```

FIGURE 24 SCENARIO A CONFIGURATIONS SELECTIONS

After making all these selections in config.yaml file and run the “snakemake” tool for Saudi Arabia, results were generated and optimised as Network Common Data Form (NetCDF), also known as “.nc file”. After that, network results were analysed and browsed in Jupyter Lab, via which most of the graphs are generated.

FIGURE 25 SCENARIO A'S OPTIMISATION FOR INSTALLED CAPACITY BY FUEL IN 2030

Figure 25 shows the optimal generation capacity distribution, where renewables capacities reach 178.1 GW, 124.2 GW for solar PV system and 53.9 GW for onshore wind with a negligible value for offshore wind energy connected through HVDC. Looking at table 8 and figure 25, it is clearly seen that gas and oil power generation capacities were not extended as conventional power capacity remains at 131.57 GW, and that is due to the selections made in configuration file shown in figure 24. In order to show how these capacities are contributing to the 2030 electricity generation, figure 26 depicts those contributions with a total generation of 529.56 TWh, where gas-fired generation accounts for almost 43% of the total generation and renewables accounts for approximately 57%, which nearly matches the objectives of the kingdom of having a 50% renewable generation and 50% gas by 2030.

FIGURE 26 SCENARIO A'S OPTIMISATION FOR ELECTRICITY GENERATION BY FUEL IN 2030

Although oil was not excluded in this scenario, its presence is minimal due to the cost and emissions-driven optimisation, which is in full alignment with the Kingdom's vision of displacing liquid fuel from the energy mix by 2030. In the pie chart, a small amount of offshore wind turbine DC-connected-system is contributing, yet very negligible due to high cost.

FIGURE 27 SIMPLIFIED HIGH VOLTAGE (HV) OVERHEAD TRANSMISSION LINE IN SAUDI ARABIA (10 CLUSTERS/LINKPOINTS)

Due to the low clustering chosen for this scenario as shown in figure 24, 10 clusters, transmissions lines were simplified and connected with 10 link points. A 380 kV overhead transmission line are spread over the kingdom with a length of 7,145.8 circuit-kilometres (ckt-km) generated by the model, as shown in figure 27. In chapter 2 section 2.2.2 figure 13, the actual length of the 380 kV overhead transmission line was presented from Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority annual report as approximately 43,687 ckt-km. This discrepancy exists due to the need of grid simplification during running the model and optimising the network as the clustering in this scenario was as low as 10.

5.2 Scenario B (Renewable-Oriented)

Scenario A has shown an optimisation that lead to almost equal split between gas and renewables. It is necessary in this scenario to assess a heavy-renewable-oriented scenario, multiple selections in the configuration file will be changed compared to scenario A in order to have more emphasis on renewables with stricter CO₂ limit in order to cover the most possible pathways. As per the vision 2030 goals, liquid fuel will be removed from the power energy mix by 2030. Therefore, this scenario is run using the “snakemake -j1 solve_all_networks” tool with the following modifications in the configuration file: 1- Removing oil from the “conventional_carriers” along with other unnecessary carriers, 2- Removing offshore wind from the “renewable_carriers”, 3- Making solar and onshore wind “extendable_carriers”, 4-

Filter out all powerplants with date out before 2030, 5- Adding the announced solar and wind farms shown in Appendix A to “custom_powerplants.csv” and enable it by toggling it to “merge”, 6- Setting a CO₂ limit of 51.875 Mt in “co2_limit”, 7- Increasing spatiotemporal resolution to 30 clusters through “clusters”, 8- Removing combined cycle gas turbines (CCGT) from extendable carriers, and 9- Keep other settings as scenario A. Figure 28 shows those modification in the “config.yaml”.

```

load_options:
  ssp: "ssp2-2.6"
  weather_year: 2013
  prediction_year: 2030
  scale: 1

electricity:
  base_voltage: 380.
  voltages: [132., 220., 300., 380., 500., 750.]
  co2limit: 5.1875e+7

scenario:
  simpl: [""]
  ll: ["copt"]
  clusters: [30]
  opts: [Co2L-3h]
  planning_horizons:
    - 2030

electricity:
  extendable_carriers:
    Generator: [solar, onwind]
    StorageUnit: []
    Store: [battery, H2]
    Link: []

  powerplants_filter: (DateOut >= 2030)
  custom_powerplants: merge

  conventional_carriers: [CCGT]
  renewable_carriers: [solar, onwind]

  estimate_renewable_capacities:
    stats: "irena"
    year: 2023
    p_nom_min: 1
    p_nom_max: false

costs:
  year: 2030
  version: v0.12.0
  discontrate: [0.071]

```

FIGURE 28 SCENARIO B CONFIGURATIONS SELECTIONS

After making all these configurations changes and adding the announced renewable projects in “custom_powerplants.csv” which then be merged into the existing conventional power plants data in “powerplants.csv”, the model has been run to generate the “.nc file”, as it was recorded that this scenario took 125 iterations to solve and optimise, which then analysed via Jupyter lab.

FIGURE 29 SCENARIO A INSTALLED CAPACITY BY CARRIER IN SAUDI ARABIA BY 2030

Figure 29 shows the optimised capacity distribution for Saudi Arabia in 2030, where solar is taking up to 36%, 35% for onshore wind, and 29% for gas-fired power using CCGT. Due to some land use constrains which has limited solar expansion and led to having wind with almost equal share of installed capacity. The capacity factor of solar usually ranges between 15-25% while wind turbines has a slightly higher capacity factor at a range of 25%-35% but due to the average wind speed across the kingdom as discussed in chapter 3, wind may perform at its lowest range of the capacity factor around 25-30% which is still higher than solar's capacity factor. Therefore, it is expected that the dispatched energy from wind all over the year would be higher than solar in terms of TWh.

FIGURE 30 SCENARIO B SAUDI 2030 ELECTRICITY GENERATION BY CARRIER

As multiple constrains were put to increase the renewables involvement, the optimisation results show that 73.9% from the total energy dispatched in 2030 is from renewables, while the remaining is gas using CCGT technology, representing almost one-quarter of the mix as shown in figure 30. Onshore wind energy has the biggest share at almost 43%.

FIGURE 31 SIMPLIFIED MODEL OF HIGH VOLTAGE (HV) OVERHEAD TRANSMISSION LINE IN SAUDI ARABIA (30 CLUSTERS/LINK POINTS)

In this scenario the number of clusters has been increased from 10, in scenario A, to 30 clusters, which shows more links and coverage all over the kingdom. Figure 31 shows the high voltage overhead transmission line connecting multiple buses and cities with a total length of 11,455.48 circuit-kilometres (ckt-km) generated by the model, which is still way less than the actual 380 kV transmission line as per Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority (SERA) is 43,687 ckt-km. Table 9 below shows a comparison between scenario A, B, and SERA’s data.

TABLE 9 TRANSMISSION LINE LENGTH, MODELLED VS ACTUAL

	PyPSA-Modelled Scenario A	PyPSA-Modelled Scenario B	SERA’s Report [5]
<i>380 kV Transmission Line</i>	7,145.8 ckt-km	11,455.4 ckt-km	43,687 ckt-km

Such simplification is for sure playing a role in slight variations, yet is needed to conduct optimisation for a whole country’s power grid in 2030.

Chapter 6: Results and Discussion

6.1 Electricity Demand Profile

Figure 32 below shows the demand profile for the modelled power systems in Saudi Arabia in 2030 which was generated part of both scenarios showing an increase of the actual demand profile in 2023 is taken from Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority (SERA)'s annual report shown in chapter 2 section 2.2.2 figure 12.

FIGURE 32 MODELLED SAUDI 2030 POWER GRID DEMAND PROFILE (TOTAL GENERATED OVER TIME IN GW)

SERA has shown a monthly demand profile in 2023, shown in figure 12, peaking in mid-August with a demand of 70.3 GW, with a least demand value in February of 28 GW, and with an average across the year of 46.4 GW [5]. As for the modelled power system in Saudi Arabia there have been an increase in the demand profile as shown in figure 33 below, where the peak being recorded in end of June at almost 89 GW, lowest demand is in January at 38.6 GW, and the average across the year is almost 60.5 GW which is 30% higher than SERA's 2023 data which is an expected growth from 2023 to 2030.

FIGURE 33 MODELLED SAUDI 2030 POWER GRID MONTHLY GENERATION DEMAND PROFILE STATISTICS

A clear comparison graph is shown in figure 34, where both PyPSA modelled Saudi demand profile and SERA's report actual data are plotted, showing the difference between 2023 demand profile and the modelled demand profile in 2030.

FIGURE 34 AVERAGE MONTHLY DEMAND PROFILE: PYPASA 2030 MODEL VS SERA ACTUAL DATA 2023

6.2 Optimisation Scenarios Results

The main aim of this thesis is to achieve a low-carbon and cost-effective power systems in Saudi Arabia by 2030. Therefore, in this section, more focus will be given towards cost, as in LCOE, and CO₂ emissions as both scenarios, A and B, will be assessed by the levelised cost of electricity achieved through their optimised network, as well as the amount of CO₂ emitted from their generation pathways.

6.2.1 Scenario A Results

In this scenario, a CO₂ limit has been imposed with an amount of 77.5 Mt, along with other scenario selections as discussed in section 5.1. The model has been able to calculate the CO₂ emissions and levelised cost of electricity (LCOE) using the data embedded in PyPSA-Earth work packages which is presented earlier in chapter 4 section 4.4 table 7.

FIGURE 35 SCENARIO A MODELLED SAUDI 2030 GENERATION AND ASSOCIATED CO₂ EMISSIONS BY CARRIER

Figure 35 depicts the amount of CO₂ emitted from the modelled power network of Saudi Arabia in 2030 with 44.83 Mt of CO₂ from gas-fired generation and a negligible 0.07 Mt of CO₂ from oil-fired generation leading to a total of 44.9 Mt of CO₂. Although a cap of 77.5 Mt of CO₂ emissions has been applied in the configuration file “config.yaml” through “co2limit”, yet the total emissions has not reached that maximum cap as the optimisation found that the most optimal and least-cost network has a much less CO₂ emissions than the applied limit.

TABLE 10 SCENARIO A MODELLED SAUDI 2030 POWER NETWORK OVERVIEW WITH LCOE RESULTS

	Capacity (GW)	Generation (TWh)	Capacity Factor (%)	CO ₂ Emissions (Mt)	LCOE (USD cents/kWh)
<i>Gas</i>	96.80	226.40	26.7	44.83	10.08
<i>Oil</i>	34.77	0.29	0.10	0.07	547
<i>Solar</i>	124.20	184.99	17	0.00	3.7
<i>Onshore Wind</i>	53.89	117.72	24.94	0.00	5.08
<i>Offshore Wind</i>	0.12	0.16	14.88	0.00	19.3
Total	309.78	529.56	N/A	44.9	6.97

Table 10 shows an overview of the modelled network of scenario A for the Saudi Arabian power network in 2030 including the LCOE for each carrier using the data presented previously in table 7. The overall levelised cost of electricity (LCOE) for the network is at almost 6.97 cents/kWh. Solar and onshore wind has clearly outperformed the others, while oil has the highest LCOE at 547 cents/kWh, and this high number is resulted because of the very low capacity factor as indicated in equation 3 earlier in the thesis.

6.2.2 Scenario B Results

More focus on renewables has been applied to this scenario, such as limiting the CO₂ emissions to 51.8 Mt, a lower limit than scenario A, as well as only having renewables as extendable carriers, which will limit the contribution from gas, while oil is totally excluded from power mix in this scenario.

FIGURE 36 SCENARIO B MODELLED SAUDI 2030 GENERATION AND ASSOCIATED CO₂ EMISSIONS BY CARRIER

Figure 36 depicts that optimisation of this scenario has led to have the emissions contributed by gas is 25.94 Mt of CO₂, which is less than the CO₂ limit by half, using an intensity factor of 0.198 t/MWh. Such a drop in emissions is expected as the goal of this scenario is to apply more renewables to the grid. Table 11 below will illustrate the costs implication of scenario B.

TABLE 11 SCENARIO B MODELLED SAUDI 2030 POWER NETWORK OVERVIEW WITH LCOE RESULTS

	Capacity (GW)	Generation (TWh)	Capacity Factor (%)	CO₂ Emissions (Mt)	LCOE (USD cents/kWh)
<i>Gas</i>	85.88	138.7	18.44	25.94	10.95
<i>Solar</i>	107	164.36	17.54	0.00	3.65
<i>Onshore Wind</i>	104.78	227.6	24.80	0.00	5.5
<i>Total</i>	297.65	530.66	N/A	25.94	6.36

Table 11 shows a comprehensive overview of scenario B results after optimisation, as the system levelised cost of electricity (LCOE) in this scenario went slightly down to 6.36 cents/kWh. LCOE and emissions figures were calculated through the notebook using PyPSA-Earth embedded cost data shown previously in table 7.

6.3 Discussion

In this study, two scenarios were developed for Saudi Arabia’s 2030 power system in order to reflect the national targets of vision 2030 and to test the possibility of increasing renewable energy shares while keeping the system reliable and cost-effective. The demand profile generated by the model showed a realistic pattern with total generation reaching about 530 TWh, which is consistent with other studies, although the timing of the peak differed from actual SERA data where the highest demand was in August while the model showed June, likely because the weather data used was from 2013. Despite this, the demand growth and seasonal variations were well aligned with expectations for 2030. These scenarios also provide a useful basis for further exploration, especially when considering future technologies such as CCUS, which, as discussed in chapter 3 section 3.2.1, is expected to capture 9 MtCO₂ annually by 2027 and expand to 44 MtCO₂ by 2035, making it highly relevant to both scenarios as it would further reduce the emissions of the power mix.

Scenario A included a wide range of technologies, keeping oil and conventional fuels, and it used 10 clusters approach which put this scenario in a simplified form, and the results showed an almost balanced mix of gas and renewables, with gas at 43% and renewables at 56%, closely matching vision 2030 target of 50% renewable generation and 50% gas-fired power. Oil was kept but its contribution was minimal, which reflects the cost and emissions-driven optimization of the model. Scenario B introduced stricter limits on conventional generation and placed more weight on renewables, resulting in about 74% renewables and only 26% from gas.

Within this scenario, wind generation became dominant compared to solar, which was unexpected and likely explained by internal land–use constraints that limited solar expansion as solar output was consistent in both scenarios, while wind output varied significantly and drove the overall difference which indicates that a land-use limit occurred for solar.

The country aims to achieve 50% of its electricity coming from renewables as the planned capacity to reach is 130GW most of which is from solar energy. Therefore, a non-simulated scenario to conduct LCOE calculation and CO₂ emissions for the vision 2030 plan is done in the table below using the costs embedded in PyPSA in order to unify the resources. This vision case LCOE is a quick post check using PyPSA cost inputs and projected generation only, and using the Jupyter lab. I did not build or optimize this scenario in PyPSA, so model constraints, siting limits, and network effects do not apply. It’s just for discussion, capacity factors may be unrealistic, technical feasibility is untested, and system emissions is higher than in the optimized scenarios.

TABLE 12 SCENARIO VISION 2030 POWER NETWORK OVERVIEW WITH LCOE RESULTS

	Capacity (GW)	Generation (TWh)	Capacity Factor (%)	CO₂ Emissions (Mt)	LCOE (USD cents/kWh)
<i>Gas</i>	100	265	30.25	50.085	8.9
<i>Solar</i>	78	159	23.27	0.00	2.8
<i>Onshore Wind</i>	52	106	23.27	0.00	6
<i>Total</i>	230	530	N/A	50.085	6.5

Table 12 shows an emission of almost 50.1 CO₂, with levelised cost of electricity at 6.5 cents/kWh, which falls in between scenario A’s LCOE and scenario B’s LCOE. This scenario could be almost reached if CO₂ limit was set higher than 77.5 Mt. As for some reason, PyPSA takes the limit and reduce it internally and that’s why scenarios achieved way less than the applied limit, in addition to the effect of optimisation.

6.4 2030 Sensitivity Analysis

The modelling part of the thesis was based on simple methodologies to assess the power grid in Saudi Arabia by 2030, as the grid was clustered down to 10-30 link points all over the Kingdom. Power plants data was different from actual data published on Saudi Electricity Regulation Authority (SERA) as shown in table 8, modelled transmission lengths were way

lower than actual 380kV transmission length shown in SERA's annual report. Such discrepancy may considerably affect the accuracy of the results and its applicability. For instance, the optimised results in scenario B led to huge growth in wind energy, and due to the cited average wind speed in chapter 3 for the Kingdom, this could probably happen due to internal land-use constraints which limited solar growth. Most of the data used throughout the modelling is based on the integrated data within PyPSA-Earth, such as cost, GDP growth, population growth, and potentials, those data are well-sources and referenced through PyPSA packages, however data usually varies from source to source. Notably, demand growth to reach around 530 TWh in both scenarios is acceptable and based on a series of credible forecasting processes through PyPSA.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and Recommendation

7.1 Conclusion

The thesis offered a strategic analysis of a sustainable power system in Saudi Arabia by 2030, though getting in depth in studying the energy landscape in Saudi Arabia, assessing its national potential of renewables, and offering a modelling using PyPSA-Earth as a tool with embedded data. Two scenarios were explored, showing that a balanced mix of gas and renewables is technically achievable and broadly consistent with vision 2030 targets. Total generation and LCOE values were found to be in line with international studies, which supports the credibility of the approach despite its reliance on simplified inputs.

Saudi Arabia is already making major steps to advance its energy system towards a more sustainable future, with large scale renewable deployment, expansion of CCUS, and wider grid investments. The results here underline that such progress can be accelerated by policy actions, such as redirecting fuel subsidies to further promote renewables.

In this thesis the renewable options studies were solar PV along with onshore and offshore wind. Other resources like CSP, waste, and nuclear were not under the focus in this dissertation, yet they hold promising potentials and could be further assessed. The study remains a first step, limited by data depth and simplifications, but it demonstrates that high renewable penetration is both realistic and cost-effective. It should be seen as useful reference for researchers and policymakers to support the Saudi transition towards its net zero by 2060.

7.2 Recommended Future Work

Future research should expand the modelling framework by incorporating a wider set of low-carbon technologies, particularly CCUS and DAC, which are expected to play a critical role in Saudi Arabia's decarbonisation pathway by 2030. Their integration into PyPSA would allow a more realistic assessment of emissions reduction options alongside renewables and gas, it also play a significant role in reshaping some of the data such as cost implication which would lead to different LCOE system, also its effect on gas generation efficiency once integrated. CSP and nuclear resources could be assessed in future modelling opportunities as they have a considerable potential in the Kingdom. Future modelling could also rely on integrating government published data with PyPSA, such as for demand, transmission, and generation, that would increase the accuracy of the results.

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Chapter 9: Appendices

A. Saudi Arabia's Renewable Energy Projects Portfolio [11].

<i>Project Name</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Expected Commissioning</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Capacity (GW)</i>	<i>LCOE cents/kWh</i>
<i>Sakaka</i>	Installed	2020	Solar	0.3	2.3417
<i>Dumat Al-Jandal</i>	Installed	2022	Wind	0.4	2.13
<i>Rabigh 1</i>	Installed	2023	Solar	0.3	1.7016368
<i>Jeddah</i>	Installed	2023	Solar	0.3	1.624112
<i>Sudair</i>	Installed	2023	Solar	1.5	1.239
<i>Layla</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.091	2.98
<i>Saad 1</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.3	1.48267
<i>Shuaibah 1</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.6	1.04
<i>Ar Rass 1</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	0.7	1.49867
<i>Shuaibah 2</i>	Installed	2024	Solar	2.06	1.79
<i>Saad 2</i>	Installed	2025	Solar	1.125	1.792
<i>Wadi Aldawaser</i>	Installed	2025	Solar	0.112	1.87
<i>Kahfah</i>	Installed	2025	Solar	1.425	1.768
<i>Ar Rass 2</i>	Partially Installed (1GW)	2025	Solar	2	1.696
<i>Rabigh 2</i>	Under Development	2026	Solar	0.3	1.78138
<i>Henakiyah 2</i>	Under Development	2026	Solar	0.4	1.51631
<i>Tabarjal</i>	Under Development	2026	Solar	0.4	1.70795
<i>Waad Al Shammal</i>	Under Development	2026	Wind	0.5	1.70187
<i>Alghat</i>	Under Development	2026	Wind	0.6	1.56558
<i>Henakiyah 1</i>	Under Development	2026	Solar	1.1	1.6842
<i>Sufun</i>	Tendered	2027	Solar	0.4	
<i>Samtah</i>	Tendered	2027	Solar	0.6	
<i>Al Darb</i>	Tendered	2027	Solar	0.6	
<i>Al Masa'a</i>	Under Development	2027	Solar	1	1.36861
<i>Khushaybi</i>	Under Development	2027	Solar	1.5	1.67289
<i>As Sdawi</i>	Under Development	2027	Solar	2	1.2926
<i>Haden</i>	Under Development	2027	Solar	2	1.58762
<i>Muwayh</i>	Under Development	2027	Solar	2	1.60852
<i>Yanbu</i>	Under Development	2027	Wind	0.7	1.72

<i>Shaqra</i>	Under Development	2028	Wind	1	1.866
<i>Najran</i>	Tendered	2028	Solar	1.4	
<i>Dwadmi</i>	Tendered	2028	Wind	1.5	
<i>Khulis</i>	Under Development	2028	Solar	2	1.36117
<i>Starah</i>	Under Development	2028	Wind	2	2.05712
<i>Afif 1</i>	Under Development	2028	Solar	2	1.26596
<i>Afif 2</i>	Under Development	2028	Solar	2	1.25959
<i>Bisha</i>	Under Development	2028	Solar	3	1.28989
<i>Al Humaij</i>	Under Development	2028	Solar	3	1.30848
<i>Khushaybi</i> 2	Tendered	2029	Solar	0.5	
<i>Henakiyah</i> 3	Tendered	2029	Solar	1.5	
<i>Haden 2</i>	Tendered	2029	Solar	2	
<i>Muwayh 2</i>	Tendered	2029	Solar	2	
<i>As Sdawi</i> 2	Tendered	2029	Solar	3	

B. Modelling tools analysis

1. Analysis conducted for 75 energy modelling tools, highlighting the four tools assessed in this thesis [49].

List of models included in the review, their full name, who they are developed/published by, availability (AV), necessary software and references. Abbreviations used in the availability column: C – Comm demo version, F – Free, OS – Open-Source, AC – Free academic version, UN – Unknown (/not yet decided), ED – Free for educational purposes, UR – Upon Request.

Model	#	Full-name	Published/Developed by	AV	Software
AURORAmp	1	–	EPIS	C (D, A)	Stand-alone
BALMOREL	2	–	Hans Ravn	OS	JAMS + Solver
Calliope	3	–	ETH Zürich - Stefan Pfenniger	OS	Python
CASPOC	4	–	Simulation Research Netherlands	C (D)	Stand-alone
COMPETES	5	Comprehensive Market Power in Electricity Transmission and Energy Simulator	Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands	A ^a	AIMMS/GUROBI
COMPOSE	6	Compare Options for Sustainable Energy	Morten Blarke, ENERGIANALYSE.DK	A, C	Stand-alone ^b
CYME	7	–	CYME International	C (T)	Stand-alone
DER-CAM	8	Distributed Energy Resources Customer Adoption Model	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	F	Online – None, Licensed – GAMS
DESSinEE	9	Demand for Energy Services, Supply and Transmission in Europe	Imperial College London - Iain Staffell, Richard Green	OS	Excel/VBA
DIETER*	10	Dispatch and Investment Evaluation Tool with Endogenous Renewables	DIW Berlin - Alexander Zerrahn & Wolf-Peter Schill	OS	GAMS + Solver
DigSILENT/PowerFactory	11	Digital Simulation of Electrical NeTworks - Power Factory	DigSilent GmbH	C	Stand-Alone
EMLab- Generation	12	Energy Modelling Laboratory - Generation	TU Delft - Richtstein, Chappin, Bhagwat & de Vries	OS	JAVA & Maven
EMMA	13	The European Electricity Market Model	Neon Neue Energieökonomik GmbH - Lion Hirth	OS	GAMS/CPLEX
EMPIRE	14	European Model for Power system Investment with Renewable Energy	NTNU – Christian Skar et al.	UN	Xpress-Mosel
EMPS	15	EFIs Multi-Area Powermarket Simulator	SINTEF Energy Research	C	Stand-alone
EnergyPlan	16	–	Sustainable Energy Planning Research Group - Aalborg University	F	Stand-alone
energyPro	17	–	EMD International A/S	C	Stand-alone
Enertile ^c	18	–	Fraunhofer ISI	NA	Solver (CPLEX)
ENTIGRIS ^d	19	–	Fraunhofer ISE – Christoph Kost	NA	GAMS
ETM (1)	20	EUROfusion Times Model	EUROfusion	UN	GAMS/CPLEX, VEDA-FE & VEDA-BE
ETM (2)	21	Energy Transition Model	Quintel Intelligence	OS	Online tool
ETSAP-TIAM	22	The TIMES Integrated Assessment Model	ETSAP-IEA	F ^e	GAMS/CPLEX, Excel, VEDA-FE & VEDA-BE
EUCAD	23	European Unit Commitment and Dispatch	Univ. Grenoble Alpes – Jacques Després	NA	GAMS/CPLEX
EUPower-Dispatch	24	–	Carlo Brancucci Martínez-Anido (European Commission, JRC)	UN	GAMS/CPLEX (MATLAB)
ficus	25	–	TUM EI EWK – Dennis Atabay	OS	Python
GCAM	26	Global Change Assessment Model	PNNL	OS	BOOST, XERCES, JAVA, HECTOR
GEM-E3	27	General Equilibrium Model for Economy-Energy-Environment	European Commission Funded Multinational Collaboration	NA	GAMS (Solved with PATH)
GENESYS	28	Genetic Optimisation of a European Energy Supply System	RWTH-Aachen University – Alvarez, Bussar, Cai, Chen, Moraes Jr., Stöcker, Thien +	OS	Stand-alone
GridLAB-D	29	–	U.S. Department of Energy	OS	Stand-alone
HOMER	30	Hybrid Optimisation of Multiple Energy Resources	NREL – Peter Lilienthal	C (T)	Stand-alone
HYPERSIM	31	–	Opal-RT	C	Stand-alone
IHOGA	32	Improved Hybrid Optimisation by Genetic Algorithms	Dr. Rodolfo Dufo-López - University of Zaragoza	ED (C) (pro +)	Stand-alone
IMAKUS	33	Iteratives Modell zur Ausbauplanung von Kraftwerken und Speichern	Technische Universität München - Philipp Kuhn	UN	MATLAB/CPLEX MATLAB/GUROBI
INVERT/EE-Lab	34	–	EEG - Vienna University of Technology	NA	Python
IPSA 2	35	Interactive Power System Analysis	IPSA Power	C	Stand-alone
IRIE	36	Integrated Regulating power market in Europe	NTNU (within a SINTEF project)	UR	AMPL - CPLEX/GUROBI & EMPS
LEAP	37	Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning	Stockholm Environment Institute	NA	SA
LIBEMOD	38	Liberalization MODEL for the European Energy Markets	Frisch Centre & the Research Department at Statistics Norway	F	GAMS
LIMES-EU	39	Long-term Investment Model for the Electricity Sector	Potsdam Institute for Climate Research - Paul Nahmmacher	UN	GAMS/CPLEX
LOADMATCH*	40	LOADMATCH Grid Integration Model	M. Z. Jacobson et al.	UN	UN
LUSYM	41	Leuven University System Modelling	K. Van den Bergh et al.	UR	GAMS (MATLAB)
MARKAL	42	MARKET ALlocation model	IEA-ETSAP	C (D)	GAMS + Solver (VEDA)

(continues)

Model	#	Full-name	Published/Developed by	AV	Software
MESSAGE	43	Model for Energy Supply Strategy Alternatives and their General Environmental Impact	IIASA	UR	GAMS & ORACLE
NEMO	44	National Electricity Market Optimiser	UNSW - Ben Elliston	OS	Python
NEMS	45	National Energy Modelling System	U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA)	F ^f	–
Oemof (SOLPH)	46	Open Energy Modelling Framework	Oemof developing group (Reiner Lemoine Institut/ZNES Flensburg/OVGU)	OS	Python + Solver
OpenDSS	47	Open Distribution System Simulator	Electric Power Research Institute	OS	Stand-alone
OsEMOSYS	48	The Open Source Energy Modelling System	KTH - Howells et al.	OS	GNU MathProg
PLEXOS	49	PLEXOS Integrated Energy Model	Energy Exemplar - Glenn Drayton	C (A)	Stand-alone
POLES	50	Prospective Outlook on Long-term Energy Systems	CNRS (GAEL Energy), Enerdata, JRC-IPTS	NA	N.A.
PowerGAMA	51	Power Grid and Market Analysis	SINTEF Energy Research - Harald G. Svendsen	OS	Python
PRIMES*	52	Price-Induced Market Equilibrium System	ESM/Lab/ICCS at the Technical University of Athens	NA	–
ProdRisk	53	–	SINTEF Energy Research	NA	Fortran + COIN-CLP/CPLEX
PyPSA	54	Python for Power System Analysis	FIAS - Tom Brown et al.	OS	Python
RAPSim	55	Renewable Alternative Powersystems Simulation	NES, AUU - Pöschacker, Khatib, Elmenreich et al.	OS	Stand-alone
ReEDS	56	Regional Energy Deployment System	NREL	NA	GAMS (Excel & R)
ReMIND	57	Regional Model of Investments and Development	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	NA	GAMS/CONOPT
REMIX	58	Renewable Energy Mix	DLR	NA	GAMS
renpass	59	Renewable Energy Pathways Simulation System	Frauke Wiese & Gesine Bökenkamp	OS	MySQL, R, RMySQL
RETScreen	60	The RETScreen Clean Energy Project Analysis Software	Natural Resources Canada	F	Windows with .NET
SAM	61	System Advisor Model	U.S. Department of Energy and NREL	F	Stand-alone
SIMPOW	62	Simulation of Power Systems	Solvina	C (D)	Stand-alone
SIREN	63	"Sustainable Energy Now" Integrated Renewable Energy Network	Sustainable Energy Now Inc. - Angus King	OS	Stand-alone
SNOW ^g	64	Statistics Norway's World model	Statistics Norway	F	GAMS & MPSGE
stELMOD	65	Stochastic Electricity Market Model	Jan Abrell (ETH Zürich) & Friedrich Kunz (DIW Berlin)	OS	GAMS/CPLEX
SWITCH	66	Solar, Wind, Transmission, Conventional generation and Hydroelectricity	Fripp, Johnston & Maluenda	OS	Python
Temoa	67	Tools for Energy Model Optimisation and Analysis	NC State University - K. Hunter et al.	OS	Python + Solver
TIMES	68	The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System	IEA-ETSAP	C (D)	GAMS + Solver (VEDA)
TIMES-Norway	69	As TIMES	IFE/NVE	j	GAMS, CPLEX/XPRESS
TIMES-Oslo	70	As TIMES	IFE	k	GAMS, CPLEX/XPRESS
TRNSYS18	71	TRNSient SYstem Simulation	TESS, SEL, UW, CSTB, TRANSSOLAR	C (D)	Stand-alone
urbs	7372	–	TUM (Hamacher, Huber & Dorfner)	OS	Python (Solver)
WEM*	73	World Energy Model	International Energy Agency	NA	Vensim + others
WeSiM	74	Whole-electricity System Investment Model	Imperial College of London	NA	Unknown
WITCH	75	World Induced Technical Change Hybrid model	FEEM	UR	GAMS

^a Own tool of ECN used for quantitative analysis for EU or national projects (it could also be freely used for research by academia with whom ECN cooperates).

^b Good performance open-source MILP solver included (COINMP), commercial solver license recommended (e.g. CPLEX or GUROBI).

^c Previously called PowerACE.

^d Previously RESLion.

^e Free of charge for Institutes appointed by one of the Contracting Partners of ETSAP.

^f Free for students. Free for country government, NGO or academics in developing countries. Commercial for Academic, non-consulting and consulting in OECD countries.

^g Excluding IHS Global Insight macro sub-model.

^h Intel Fortran, Eviews, IHS Global Insight model, OML & Xpress solver, GAMS & Xpress, AIMMS & CPLEX, R, MS Windows OS.

ⁱ There is both a global version and a Norwegian version of the model (SNOW-NO).

^j Not available (Except for cooperation with Ph.D. or master students).

^k Not available (Except for cooperation with Ph.D. or master students).

General logic and spatiotemporal resolution. Abbreviations used in the table: **Purpose:** IDS – Investment Decision Support, ODS – Operation Decision Support, S – Scenario, PSAT – Power System Analysis Tool, A – Analysis Approach; **BU** – Bottom-up, **TD** – Top-down, **H** – Hybrid; **Methodology:** S – Simulation, LP – Linear Programming, MIP – Mixed Integer Programming, PE – Partial Equilibrium, A – Accounting, ABS – Agent-based Simulation, MIQCP – Mixed Integer Quadratically Constrained Programming, CGE – Computable General Equilibrium, E – Equilibrium, CMA-ES – Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy, HO – Heuristic Optimisation, ECE – Economic Computable Equilibrium, SDDP – Stochastic Dual Dynamic Programming; **Temporal Resolution/Modelling Horizon/Geographical Coverage:** UD – user-defined, NL – No limitations.

Models	#	Purpose	Appr.	Methodology	Temporal resolution	Modelling horizon	Geographical coverage
AURORAxmp	1	I & ODS, S, PSAT	BU	S, LP, MIP, PE	UD (Hourly)	UD (50+ years)	Single project → Global
BALMOREL	2	I & ODS	H	PE/LP (MIP)	Hourly/Aggregate	50 years (UD)	Regional → International
Calliope	3	I & ODS	BU	LP (MIP under development)	UD	UD	UD
CASPOC	4	PSAT	BU	S	UD	µs to 1 year	Single-System/Local
COMPETES	5	I & ODS	BU	LP (In.), MIP (Op.)	Hourly	UD	National (Europe)
COMPOSE	6	ODS & S	BU	A (In.), MIP(Op.)	UD (Usually hourly)	UD	Single-Project/System
CYME	7	PSAT	BU	S	UD (Usually ms)	UD	Single-System → Regional
DER-CAM	8	I & ODS	BU	MIP	Hourly (In.) & Minutes (Op.)	Up to 20 years	Single-Project → Regional
DESSTinEE	9	S, I & ODS	BU	S	Hourly	2050	National (Europe)
DIETER*	10	I & ODS	BU	LP	Hourly	1 year	Calibrated to Germany
DigSILENT/ PowerFactory	11	PSAT	BU	S	UD	UD	Power Systems
EMLab-Generation	12	IDS	H	ABS	Yearly	2050	Two Markets/Countries
EMMA	13	I & ODS	BU	LP	Hourly	Long-term economic equilibrium	National (Europe)
EMPIRE	14	IDS	H	LP (Multi-horizon stochastic)	5 y (In.), UD time-slices per year (Op.)	Typically 40–50 y	National (Europe)
EMPS	15	I & ODS	BU	LP*	Weekly ^b	25 years	Regional → Continental
EnergyPlan	16	S, IDS	BU	S	Hourly	1 year	Local → Continental
energyPro	17	I & ODS	BU	AO ^c	Minutes	Max 40 years	Local → Regional
Enertile	18	I & ODS	BU	LP	Hourly	Usually 2050	EUMENA (National)
ENTIGRIS	19	I & ODS	BU	LP	Hourly (Op.), 5 y (In.)	2050	Regional → International
ETM (1)	20	S	BU	PE & LP	Six time slices: three seasons (winter, summer and intermediate), & day/night	2100	Global (17 regions)
ETM (2)	21	S	H	S	15-min (+ Hourly & Yearly)	2050	Community → International
ETSAP-TIAM	22	I & ODS, S	BU	LP, PE	Yearly (seasons & day-night hours)	2100	Global (15 regions)
EUCAD	23	ODS	BU	MIQCP	Hourly	Yearly	National (Europe)
EUPower-Dispatch	24	ODS	BU	MIP	Hourly	Yearly	National (Europe)
Flex	25	I & ODS	BU	MIP	Typically 15 min	1 year	Local → National
GCAM	26	S	H	PE	5 years	2100	Global (Regional)
GEM-E3	27	S	TD	CGE	5 years	2030 and 2050	Global (38 regions)
GENESYS	28	IDS	BU	CMA-ES & HO	Hourly	2050	EUMENA (National)
GridLAB-D	29	PSAT	BU	ABS	Sub-seconds – Years	3–5 Years	Local → National
HOMER	30	I & ODS	BU	S & O	Minutes	Multi-Year	Local
HYPERSIM	31	PSAT	BU	S	10 µs	UD	Single-System → Regional
IHOGA	32	I & ODS	BU	HO	Hourly	Yearly	Local
IMAKUS	33	I & ODS	BU	LP	Hourly	Several decades	Germany
INVERT/EE-Lab	34	S	BU	S	Y (In.), Monthly (Op)	2030/2050/2080	Buildings
IPSA 2	35	PSAT	BU	S	^d	-	Power Systems
IRIE	36	ODS	BU	MIP	15-min	Yearly	26 areas in Northern Europe
LEAP	37	S	H	S & LP	Yearly	Usually 20–50 years	Local → Global
LIBEMOD	38	S	H	ECE	Yearly (EI split in summer and winter season; one day split into day and night)	1 → 20 years	National (Europe)
LIMES-EU	39	S, I & ODS	H	LP	5/10 y (6 rep. days per year, 8 time slices per day)	2050	National (Europe)
LOADMATCH*	40	S	BU	S	30 s	6 years (2050–2055)	CONUS (4' × 5' WWS data)
LUSYM	41	ODS	BU	MIP	15 min/Hourly & Daily (UC)/Weekly (Scheduling)	Daily/Weekly (UC) & Yearly (Scheduling)	National
MARKAL	42	S	BU	LP/MIP, PE	Multiple years (UD time-slices within a year)	Long-term (UD)	Local → Regional
MESSAGE	43	S, IDS	H	LP	UD (Multiple years)	Long-term (50–100+ years)	Global (11 Regions)
NEMO	44	I & ODS	BU	CMA-ES & S	Hourly	Typically 1 year	National
NEMS	45	S	H	S, O, PE	Yearly	2050	Regional/National (U.S.)
Omof (SOLPH)	46	S, I & ODS	All	LP, MLP, PE	Seconds to years	UD	UD
OpenDSS	47	PSAT	BU	S	UD (1 s to 1 h)	UD	Distribution feeders/areas
OSeMOSYS	48	IDS	BU	LP	UD (intra-annual)	UD (10–100 y)	Community → Continental
PLEXOS	49	I & ODS, S, PSAT	BU	^e	UD up to 1 min (Usually hourly)	UD (1 day to 50+ years)	Single project → Global
POLES	50	S, I & ODS	H	PE/S	Yearly (Sectoral load shape for two typical days with two-hour resolution)	2050 (2100)	Global (66 regions)
PowerGAMA	51	S (IDS)	BU	S, LP	Usually hourly	Usually 1 year	Regional/National

(continued on next page)

Models	#	Purpose	Appr.	Methodology	Temporal resolution	Modelling horizon	Geographical coverage
PRIMES ^a	52	S, IIS	H	PE	Yearly	Long-term	National (Europe)
ProdRisk	53	ODS	BU	LP (SDDP)	Usually 5–25 weekly periods	Usually 3–10 years	Local → National
PyPSA	54	I & ODS, PSAT	BU	LP	Hourly	1 year	Local → Continental
RAPSim	55	PSAT	BU	S	Minutes	Multiple days	Local
ReEDS	56	S (& IIS)	BU	LP & PE	^c	2050	^b
ReMIND	57	S	H	NLP	^c	2150	Global (11 regions)
REMix	58	I & ODS	H	LP	Hourly	Typically 1 year	Regional (Germany) → National (Europe)
rempass	59	ODS, S	BU	S (In) & O (Op)	Typically Hourly	1 year	Regional/National (Western Europe)
RETScreen	60	IIS, S	H	S	Monthly/Yearly/Daily	Max 100 years	Single-system → Global
SAM	61	IIS	BU	S	Sub-Hourly	1 year (Lifetime for e.g. batteries + PV)	Single system
SIMPOW	62	PSAT	BU	S	Milliseconds	Seconds	Single-system → Local
SIREN	63	S	BU	S	Hourly	1 year	Regional/National
SNOW	64	S	H	CGE	Yearly	UD (1–100 years)	^j
stELMOD	65	ODS	BU	MIP	Hourly	1 year	National (Europe)
SWITCH	66	I & ODS	BU	MIP	Hourly Dispatch/Decadal Investment Period	UD (2050)	Regional/National ^k
Temoa	67	S	BU	LP	Yearly (With UD time-slices)	UD	Regional (UD)
TIMES	68	I & ODS	H/BU	LP/MIP, PE	Multiple years - with UD time-slices within a year	Long-term (UD)	Local - Global
TIMES-Norway	69	S, IIS (& ODS)	BU	LP	Multiple years – 260 time-slices per year	2050	Norway (Sweden optional)
TIMES-Oslo	70	S, IIS (& ODS)	BU	LP	Multiple years – 260 time-slices per year	2050	Oslo (Norway optional)
TRNSYS18	71	PSAT	BU	S & L/NLP	0.01 s to 1 h	Multiple years	Single Project → Local
urbs	72	I & ODS	BU	LP	UD (Hourly)	UD (Yearly)	Local → National
WEM ^l	73	S	H	S	Yearly ^j	2040	Global (25 Regions)
WeSIM	74	I & ODS	H	LP	Hour or half-hourly	1 h - multi years	National → Continental
WITCH	75	S, IIS	H	NLP, E	5 years	150 years	Global (13 regions (UD))

^a The model includes stochastic optimisation (Stochastic Dynamic Programming (SDP)), linear programming and simulation. In the strategy evaluation, SDP is used to calculate incremental water values and heuristics is used to treat the interaction between areas. In the simulation part of the model, total system costs are minimised in a linear problem formulation.

^b In the strategy evaluation the resolution is weekly. In the simulation it can be weekly with a load-duration curve within the week or with hourly resolution.

^c Analytical optimisation [69].

^d 30 min (Load flow analysis), Usually Milliseconds (Fault Level & Transient Stability).

^e About 1-year (Load flow), Fault levels (hundreds of milliseconds), Transient (seconds).

^f Optimisation (Mixed-Integer, Linear and Non-Linear)/Partial Equilibrium (e.g. solving Nash-Cournot with integer problems uses Mixed Integer Quadratic Programming (MIQP)).

^g Sequential 2-year periods, 17 seasonal/diurnal blocks of non-chronological aggregate hours.

^h U.S. (+ Canada & Mexico) – (134 Supply/demand balancing areas (+ 20 CA/+ 49 ME) & 356 renewable resource regions (+ 47 CA/+ 49 ME).

ⁱ 5 years until 2060, 10 until 2110, 20 until 2150.

^j Global version: Flexible, typically 2–10 regions, National version: Norway and rest of the world.

^k Models typically have 1–50 load zones; models have been created for California, Western U.S., Hawaii, Chile, Nicaragua, China and other regions.

^l A new feature in WEM 2016 is the inclusion of a more detailed power market module with hourly resolution.

Technological and economic parameters. Abbreviations used in the table: Ren. Gen: HP – Hydropower, ROR – Run-of-river, SP – Solar Power, WP – Wind Power, ST – Solar Thermal, WaP – Wave Power, GT – Geothermal, CSP – Concentrated Solar Power, TP – Tidal Power; **Storage:** PHS – Pumped Hydro Storage, CAES – Compressed Air Energy Storage, B – Batteries, H – Hydrogen, TES – Thermal Energy Storage; **Grid:** NTC – Net Transfer Capacity; **Cost:** I – Investment, O&M – Operation & Maintenance, F – Fuel, CO₂ – Carbon cost, T – Taxes, B – Balancing costs.

Models	#	Conv. Gen.	Ren. Gen.	Storage	Grid	Commodities	Demand sectors	Demand elasticity	DR	Costs	Market	Emissions
AURORAxmp	1	All	All	All (Generic)	Import/Export, NTC, DC Load Flow (SCUC/SCOPF)	Electricity, Heat	Electricity (with Heat), interface to gas models	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B	All	Any Pollutant
BALMOREL	2	All	HP, ROR, SP, WP, ST, WaP	All	NTC	Electricity, Heat, Hydrogen & Fuels	Aggregated (Separate for Electricity and Heat)	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T, B	Spot	CO ₂ , SO ₂ and NO _x
Calliope	3	All	All	All	NTC	Electricity, Hydrogen, Heat & Fuels	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Supply/Demand	Any pollutant
CASPOC	4	All	All	All	Power Electronics & Circuit modelling, NTC/DC Simplification	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	No	NA	NA	No
COMPETES	5	All	HP, SP, WP, GT	PHS, CAES	PHS, CAES	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic/Elastic (short-term)	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B, T	Spot/Balancing (Short-term)	CO ₂
COMPOSE	6	All	All	All	None (Constraints can be parametrised)	Electricity, Heat & Fuels	Buildings, Transport & Industry (User-defined)	Inelastic	No ¹	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T, B	Spot, Balancing Markets	CO ₂
CYME	7	All	SP, WP (All)	B	Detailed Power Simulation	Electricity	Aggregated	NA	No	NA	NA	NA
DER-CAM	8	All (Except Nuclear)	All	All	Import/Export, Power Flow	Electricity & Heat	Aggregated, Electricity, Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand, Spot, Balancing Markets	CO ₂
DESStInEE	9	All	All	PHS	NTC	Electricity	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Inelastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Spot (Merit-order)	CO ₂
DIETER*	10	All (Except Nuclear & Lignite)	WP, SP	B, H, PHS, CAES	None	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B	Spot	No
DigSILENT/PowerFactory	11	All	All	All (Generic)	Detailed Power Flow	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	NA	NA	NA	No
EMLab-Generation	12	All	WP, SP (Generic)	All (Generic)	NTC	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Spot + CO ₂ market	CO ₂
EMMA	13	All	WP, SP, HP, ROR	PHS	NTC	Electricity & Heat	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B	Spot	No
EMPIRE	14	All	All (Except Tidal)	All (Generic)	NTC	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Supply/Demand	CO ₂
EMPS	15	All	All	PHS	NTC (Full Load Flow possible)	Electricity	Aggregated	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B	Spot	CO ₂
EnergyPlan	16	All	All	All	Import/Export	Electricity, Heat, Hydrogen & Fuels	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Spot	CO ₂
energyPro	17	All (Except nuclear)	All	PHS, CAES, B, TES	None	Electricity and Heat	Aggregated	Elastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B, T	Spot	CO ₂ , SO ₂ & NO _x
Enertile	18	All	All	PHS, TES, B	NTC	Electricity & Heat	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic for P2H, Inelastic otherwise	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Supply/demand	CO ₂

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Models	#	Conv. Gen.	Ren. Gen.	Storage	Grid	Commodities	Demand sectors	Demand elasticity	DR	Costs	Market	Emissions
MARKAL	42	All	HP, WP, SP, GT	PHS, (night-day storages)	NTC	Any commodity	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand (Competitive, perfect foresight)	Any
MESSAGE	43	All	All	All	Import/Export	Any commodity	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand	Any Pollutant
NEMO	44	OCGT, CCGT, Coal (CCS)	HP, WP, PV, CST, GT	PHS, B	None	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Spot	CO ₂
NEMS	45	All	All (except TP & WaP)	PHS, B, TES	Import/Export	Electricity & Heat (Partly Hydrogen in transport)	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand	CO ₂ , SO ₂ and NO _x
Oemof (SOLPH)	46	All	All	All	Import/Export, NTC	Electricity, Heat, Hydrogen & Fuels	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T, B	Supply/Demand	Any pollutant
OpenDSS	47	All (Generic)	SP (Others Generic)	All (Generic)	Full Multiphase AC Load Flow; Dynamics	Electricity	Aggregated (optionally disaggregated)	Inelastic	Yes	NA	NA	NA
OSeMOSYS	48	All	All	All	None	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B	Supply/Demand	Any Pollutant
PLEXOS	49	All	All	All (Generic)	*	Electricity (with Heat), Gas and Water	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , B	#	All (Generic)
POLES	50	All (25 explicit technologies)	All (16 explicit technologies)	PHS	None (Import/Export)	Electricity, Fuels	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand (Carbon price)	GHG
PowerGAMA	51	All (Generic)	All (Generic)	All (Generic)	Linearised DC Power Flow	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	No ^o	Marginal Costs	Supply/Demand (Perfect)	None
PRIMES*	52	All	All	All	DC linearised Optimal Power Flow	Electricity, Heat & Hydrogen	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand	CO ₂
ProdRisk	53	Thermal Power Plants	HP, WP	PHES	None (Exists a prototype with detailed grid)	Electricity	Aggregated	Yes	No	No fixed price	Spot (Capacity Market under development)	None
PyPSA	54	All	All	All (Generic)	Non-linear/Linear Power Flow, NTC	Any commodity	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	Capital Cost & Marginal Cost	Supply/Demand	CO ₂
RAPSim	55	None (Under development)	WP, SP	None (Under development)	Detailed Power Flow	Electricity	Building	Inelastic	No	None	None	None
ReEDS	56	All	All (Except Tidal)	All (Except Hydrogen)	Linearised DC Power Flow	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	#	CO ₂ , SO ₂ , NO _x + Mercury
ReMIND	57	All (Coal, Oil, Gas, Uranium, Biomass)	HP, SP, WP, GT	All (Generic)	None	Electricity, Heat, Hydrogen & Fuels	Buildings, Transport & Industry	Elastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Supply/Demand (Pareto/Nash)	Any Pollutant
REMix	58	All	All	All	NTC, DC simplification	Electricity, Heat & Hydrogen	Aggregated	Inelastic	Yes	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Supply/Demand	CO ₂
renpass	59	All	HP, WP, SP, GE, ROR	PHS, CAES, B	NTC	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂	Spot	CO ₂
RETScreen	60	All	All	B	Central/Isolated/Off-Grid (Import/Export)	Electricity & Heat	Buildings & Industry	Inelastic	No	I, O&M, F, CO ₂ , T	Supply/Demand	GHG
SAM	61	Conventional Thermal & ...	SP, ST, CSP, WP, GT	B, TES	None	Electricity	Aggregated	Inelastic	No	I, O&M, F, T	None (E.G. Power Purchase Agreement!)	None

2. Analysis conducted for 20 energy modelling tools [50].

Software	Version	Citation	Free Software	Grid Analysis			Economic Analysis								
				Power Flow	Continuation Power Flow	Dynamic Analysis	Transport Model	Linear OPF	SCLOPF	Nonlinear OPF	Multi-Period Optimisation	Unit Commitment	Investment Optimisation	Other Energy Sectors	
Power system tools	MATPOWER	6.0	[6]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓				
	NEPLAN	5.5.8	[2]		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓				✓
	pandapower	1.4.0	[9]	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓				
	PowerFactory	2017	[1]		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓				
	PowerWorld	19	[3]		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓				
	PSAT	2.1.10	[7]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓			
	PSS/E	33.10	[4]		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓				
	PSS/SINCAL	13.5	[5]		✓		✓					✓			✓
	PYPOWER	5.1.2	[8]	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓				
	PyPSA	0.11.0		✓	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓
Energy system tools	calliope	0.5.2	[11]	✓			✓				✓			✓	✓
	minpower	4.3.10	[12]	✓			✓	✓			✓		✓		
	MOST	6.0	[13]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		
	oemof	0.1.4	[14]	✓			✓				✓		✓	✓	✓
	OSeMOSYS	2017	[15]	✓			✓				✓			✓	✓
	PLEXOS	7.400	[16]				✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓
	PowerGAMA	1.1	[17]	✓			✓	✓			✓				
	PRIMES	2017	[18]				✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓
	TIMES	2017	[19]				✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓
	urbs	0.7	[20]	✓			✓				✓		✓	✓	✓

C. Monthly Clearness Index values used for Tabuk's region GHI calculation in python [27].

<i>Month</i>	<i>K_t</i>
<i>January</i>	0.52
<i>February</i>	0.55
<i>March</i>	0.57
<i>April</i>	0.62
<i>May</i>	0.57
<i>June</i>	0.54
<i>July</i>	0.53
<i>August</i>	0.55
<i>September</i>	0.52
<i>October</i>	0.56
<i>November</i>	0.55
<i>December</i>	0.51

D. AI Disclosure

None of the ideas contained in this report were generated by AI, all the work and core steps belong to the author. However, basic AI tools were used in activities such searching from various internet sources for supportive ideas. Further, AI language checking tools were utilized to eliminate major grammatical errors and to enhance academic writing only.